

Larger Terrestrial Vertebrates of NEOM Nature Reserve, NEOM, Tabuk Province, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia – A 2026 Update

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Arabian red fox

Executive Summary

Larger Terrestrial Vertebrate Survey

Larger terrestrial vertebrates of NEOM Nature Reserve, Tabuk Province, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia were surveyed from 2019 to 2024 using 248 wildlife camera traps deployed throughout NEOM in representative major ecosystems and habitats (Appendix A). Some cameras were running for months and some for years. Some survey sites were relatively remote while others were in areas of increasing development. Forty-nine cameras were lost or damaged and no data obtained from them. The total number of trap nights was 28,813 yielding 62,733 wildlife and human activity detection events and an estimated 448,611 images. An additional 232 cameras were deployed by NEOM in possible development areas from 2021 through 2024 and detected presence of several wildlife species (Appendix A). Multiple biodiversity surveys in NEOM from 2018 to 2024 were reviewed and evaluated for evidence of species occurrence. Additional wildlife detections from camera-trap deployments at 38 new localities in 2025-2026 are presented in this update.

Key Findings

Twenty-six larger terrestrial vertebrate species were detected through the combined surveys. These include Arabian wolf, Arabian red fox, Blanford's fox, Rüppell's fox, wild cat, sand cat, striped hyena, desert hedgehog, chukar, Arabian, and sand partridges, honey badger, striped hyena, Egyptian spiny-tail lizard, Nubian ibex, desert monitor, Cape hare, rock hyrax, and domestic sheep, goat, donkey, dog, cat, and camel. Caracal was possibly detected through scat only (no DNA identification). Four possible species were not detected, specifically Arabian leopard, Asiatic jackal, Indian crested porcupine, and Dorcas gazelle. One Arabian gazelle was detected outside a rewilding reserve, but this was likely an individual released from a local farm. Arabian oryx, Arabian gazelle, sand gazelle, Nubian ibex, and red-necked ostrich have been released into several enclosed rewilding reserves.

Arabian wolf, wild cat, Blanford's fox, and Nubian ibex are widely distributed and present around most foothill and montane areas. Red foxes are abundant, particularly in plains and rocky foothill habitats. Striped hyena, honey badger, sand cat, and Rüppell's fox are uncommon to rare. Lion, cheetah, Arabian leopard are top predators that are no longer in NEOM's natural ecosystems, leaving only Arabian wolf, striped hyena, honey badger, domestic dogs, desert monitor, and large birds of prey (not surveyed here) as higher-level predators.

The status of wildlife species and ecological guilds currently in NEOM supports assessing the larger terrestrial assemblage's status presently as at a transition from a diminished to a depleted state. Human activities with negative impacts on wildlife, such as livestock grazing, offroad driving, and hunting, remain prevalent. Despite this declining status, NEOM's wildlands remain extensive, diverse and stand as one of the most wildlife-rich large natural landscapes in the Kingdom with sizeable populations of several threatened species. These wildlands are a conservation priority.

Larger Terrestrial Vertebrates of NEOM Nature Reserve

This larger terrestrial vertebrate survey is intended to support wildlife conservation, protected area management, ecosystem restoration, greening, and rewilding initiatives across the NEOM Nature Reserve, Tabuk Province, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The results function as a baseline for larger terrestrial vertebrate communities and various threats and help managers monitor trends in restoration and efficacy of conservation interventions.

The larger terrestrial vertebrate fauna is defined here, for the purposes of this survey, as (i) terrestrial cursorial mammals greater than 280 grams (for example, desert hedgehog [*Paraechinus aethiopicus*], Cape hare [*Lepus capensis*], and heavier species), (ii) the Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard (*Uromastix aegyptia*) and desert monitor (*Varanus griseus*), and (iii) largely cursorial (that is, ‘ground-dwelling’) birds (bustard, ostrich, partridges) (refer to Table 1 for list of larger terrestrial mammals, birds, and reptiles expected for the NEOM Nature Reserve).

Small mammals, smaller reptiles and amphibians, most birds, and bats are not target taxa of this survey as these groups are inefficiently detected using camera-traps deployed to sample larger vertebrates. Some larger, more arboreal birds, such as brown-necked raven (*Corvus ruficollis*), fan-tailed raven (*Corvus rhipidurus*), pharaoh eagle owl (*Bubo ascalaphus*), other owls, vultures (cinereous [*Aegypius monachus*], Egyptian [*Neophron percnopterus*], lammergeier [*Gypaetus barbatus*], griffon [*Gyps fulvus*]), and multiple species of larger raptors are not considered within this survey’s set of target taxa of larger terrestrial vertebrates as they are not ‘terrestrial’ and these groups are inefficiently surveyed using unbaited camera traps, the primary technique employed in this survey.

Larger cursorial (that is, ‘ground-dwelling’) vertebrates are an important component of native ecosystems as they make up a high proportion of the animal biomass of relatively intact biotic communities and fulfil diverse ecological roles, such as larger herbivores, mesopredators, seed dispersers, top predators, ecosystem engineers, and scavengers. Relatively intact larger vertebrate assemblages confer to ecosystems resistance and resilience to short-term disturbances and long-term changes, such as changes to climate from global heating through, for example, more complex food webs and structuring vegetation that retains more moisture and carbon and provides microrefugia habitats for local adaptation.

Larger vertebrates found in desert regions are particularly vulnerable to hunting, habitat loss and fragmentation, ecosystem degradation, and anthropogenic disturbance. This is due, in part, to larger wildlife having higher minimum-area requirements to populations to survive, slower reproductive rates, and high visibility and attractiveness to hunters (see Durant et al. 2014, Vale & Brito 2015, Brito et al. 2018, Yusefi et al. 2022). They are among the first to disappear (that is, go extinct or be extirpated) from ecosystems as threats increase or persist. Larger species that inhabit

xeric ecosystems are particularly vulnerable to hunting as they may only occur in low abundance, they have less vegetative cover to find refuge in, and their exposure is high as they often require substantial movements to be able to track highly patchy resources.

The persistence, return, and revival of larger vertebrates and their ecological role throughout natural ecosystems is a strong indicator of progress and success of protected area management, ecosystem protection and restoration, landscape connectivity, and rewilding activities. Intact larger vertebrate assemblages thriving in NEOM's natural landscapes can also offer a rare and spectacular wildlife experience to NEOM's residents and visitors alike.

State of Knowledge

Larger terrestrial vertebrates of the Arabian Peninsula are well documented, including mammals (Harrison 1968, Nader 1989, 1990, Harrison & Bates 1991, Kingdon 1991, Thouless et al. 1991, Mallon & Kingswood 2001, Cunningham & Wronski 2010, Mallon and Budd [eds] 2011, Stuart & Stuart 2016, Aloufi & Eid 2019, Eid & Mallon 2021, Al Abaid et al. 2023, Mallon et al. 2023, Mensoor 2023, Al Ahmari et al. 2024, Clarke & Alsharif 2025, Eid & Abu Azam 2025, Al Hakmani et al. 2026), birds (for example, Jennings 1986, Porter & Aspinall 2010, Symes et al. 2015), and reptiles (Cox et al. 2012, Aloufi & Amr 2015, Egan 2022, Weijerman et al. 2024). Several larger terrestrial faunal surveys have been conducted for the Tabuk region, including mammals (Seddon et al. 1987, Al Nafie 1989, Aloufi et al. 2016, Aloufi & Amr 2018, McGrath & Whelan 2021, Abed et al. 2023, Roobas 2023, Bilancioni et al. 2024), birds (Alatawi et al. 2018, Sousa et al. 2024), and reptiles (Aloufi & Amr 2015, Egan et al. 2021, Egan & Whelan 2023, Licata et al. 2024), and biota, in general (Ansari et al. 2022). Elmirghani and others (2025) have compiled species lists for many taxa that are found within NEOM. This report contributes the results of several years (2019 to 2024) of wildlife surveys in NEOM to the increasing knowledge of the terrestrial vertebrate fauna of the region (Appendix A, B).

Larger Terrestrial Vertebrate Survey

Purpose

The larger terrestrial vertebrate survey had several objectives:

- 1) **A baseline for larger terrestrial vertebrates** – To establish baseline data on the diversity, status, distribution and behavior of medium-to-large terrestrial mammals and birds within the NEOM Nature Reserve. This baseline is critical to assess the efficacy and evolution of NEOM Nature Reserve's Rewilding Program and Nature Reserve ecosystem restoration ([see How Neom Nature Reserve is shaping the Kingdom's biodiversity and ecological restoration strategy](#)).
- 2) **Establish a baseline for threats to wildlife**, such as hunting, livestock overgrazing, and disturbance from other activities of humans. This baseline informs compliance and threat

diminishment efforts and allows managers to identify threat hotspots and track the impact of control efforts.

3) Help monitor wildlife and human activity in possible and confirmed wildlife corridors and the wildlife highway crossings – To provide information to guide planning, design, and operations of highways, infrastructure, and activities in localities important for the movement of wildlife to minimize disturbance and mortality of wildlife and reduce collision risk for people and vehicles.

4) Estimate the intactness of the NEOM Nature Reserve terrestrial megafauna – To provide data that can be used, along with other information, to more accurately estimate the intactness (that is, the status) of the larger terrestrial vertebrate fauna in the NEOM Nature Reserve as of 2019 to early 2024, and help monitor the status of the Outstanding Universal Values of concern for the proposed (tentative) Bioclimatic Refugia of Western Arabia UNESCO World Heritage Site (Permanent Delegation of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to UNESCO 2023).

5) Identify refugia areas – To better understand if camera-trap surveys can be used by protected area managers to identify areas within the NEOM Nature Reserve that act as spatial or temporal refugia for wildlife or deserve increased conservation action, or, conversely, are hotspots of threats to wildlife, such as hunting.

6) Contribution of camera-trap data – To better understand how data from camera-trap surveys can be used to complement and confirm that derived from other survey methods, such as distance sampling, drone-based surveys (Buckland et al. 2001, 2004), and patrol-based direct encounter or sign data.

7) Assess cost-effectiveness of camera-trap surveys – To assess the cost-effectiveness of systematic camera-trap surveys for wildlife monitoring in the NEOM Nature Reserve, particularly in terms of overall cost, time and staff requirements, and approaches that are useful to sensitize local communities and reduce camera-trap loss and failure.

METHODS

Study Area

Ecoregions & Ecosystem Types

NEOM covers approximately 26,555 km² of land and sea in the northwest of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (Fig. 1). It includes portions of three terrestrial ecoregions: Arabian desert shrublands; Eastern Mediterranean conifer-broadleaf forests and woodlands/shrublands; and North Arabian desert (Dinerstein et al. 2017), as well as portions of the Southwestern Arabian Coast freshwater ecoregion (Abell et al. 2008) and Northern and Central Red Sea marine ecoregion (Spalding et al.

2007). Six major ecosystem types (that is, subunits of ecoregions) occur within NEOM: Northern Red Sea and Gulf of Aqaba marine, which extends from nearshore reefs and seagrass meadows to abyssal brine pools, Coastal Lowlands (comprised of drift deposits of wadi and aeolian sands, gravel sheets, granitic sand bowls, raised reef limestone, sandstone outcrops, and limestone-based deposits), Madyan Range granitic and volcanic mountains reaching to 2,580 m, Hisma Desert (a distinct zone of outcropping sandstone and drift deposits comprising wadi alluvium and aeolian sand that extends northward to Wadi Rum in Jordan and southwards to Wadi al-Disah in the Prince Mohammed bin Salman Royal Reserve), the Tabuk Sandstone tablelands, and Harrat (*harrah*) lava plateaus (basalt cobbles overlying sandstone) (Vincent 2008, Miller & Clarke 2021, Fig. 1). Substrates are largely unaltered parent rock. Only at the highest elevations (above ca. 1,800 m) has there been obvious creation of organic soil layers.

NEOM harbors eleven of the 65 terrestrial and freshwater ecosystem types and marine ecosystem types clusters identified in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's (KSA) revised protected area system plan (NCW 2024): Gulf of Al 'Aqabah Cluster; Northern Red Sea Cluster; Red Sea Mangroves; Northern Red Sea Shoreline; North Tihamah Coastal Plain; Madyan Hills and Mountains; Madyan, Hisma, and Harrat ar-Raha Mountain Summits; Hisma Plateau; Northern Sandstone Plain and Plateaus; Northwestern Harrahs; and Hijaz and Madyan Montane Wadis. Here, we use an adapted, simplified version of these eleven ecosystem types that maps six major ecosystem types (Fig. 1).

Arabian wolf

Figure 1. Major ecosystem types of NEOM: (1) Northern Red Sea & Gulf of Aqaba; (2) Coastal Lowlands; (3) Madyan Range; (4) Hisma Desert; (5) Tabuk Sandstone; and (6) Harrat lava fields. (Adapted from NCW 2024).

Physiographic Regions

NEOM's physiographic regions include the following (in accordance with Vincent 2008):

Marine

NEOM encompasses approximately 3,724 km² of the Gulf of Aqaba and northern Red Sea. The eastern coast of the Gulf of Aqaba supports narrow fringing reefs and seagrass meadows, in places. Both quickly fall away to depths reaching 1,850m within a few kilometers from the coast. The marine ecosystems from Ras Alsheik Hamid to Sharma are complex with broad seagrass meadows, fringing reefs, coral bommies, uplifted limestone islands, and enclosed bays. Here abundant groundwater infusions modify marine ecosystems and strong prevailing northerly winds help isolate marine communities. Further south along the coast the marine ecosystems are northerly extensions of the fringing and offshore reefs characteristic of much of the eastern Red Sea coast.

Coastal and near-coastal plains

The coastal and near-coastal plain constitute the northern-most section of the Tihamah Plain, a near-coastal plain with lowlands that runs more or less the entire length of the western coast of Arabia. South of Jeddah it widens to a maximum of 40 km. It is much narrower and discontinuous in NEOM (approximately 4,648 km² in NEOM), and this is especially true along the Gulf of Aqaba. Most of the plains are covered by Quaternary and Tertiary gravel and cobble deposits.

Red Sea Escarpment

The Madyan Mountains of the Red Sea Escarpment, in the northwest of the Kingdom occupy a substantial part of the NEOM area (approximately 9,022 km²). The Quaternary and Tertiary gravel deposits characteristic of the near-coastal zone ends abruptly and mountains of the Arabian Shield (i.e. composed of ancient, Precambrian rock) predominate. More conspicuous vegetation growth (i.e. with relatively dense tree and / or dwarf shrub cover) is associated with the larger wadis at lower to medium elevations, but above 1,500 m, the gentle slopes can also support species rich dwarf shrub / perennial herb communities, with scattered trees a conspicuous feature at the highest elevations.

Hisma

The Hisma Desert is a high-elevation sandstone plateau with spectacular Permo-Triassic sandstone buttes and mesas that are scattered across the plain, rising from red sands. Such rocky exposures are typical inselberg habitats that, in some cases, can constitute important refuges for both flora and fauna. The original sandstone landscape is a highly eroded plateau, and this has given rise to numerous canyons. In some areas, the sandstone rock has been weathered to ground-level, giving rise to a characteristic sandstone pavement landscape (Brown & Ayasrah 2023). This covers an area of about 6,487 km² in NEOM alone and constitutes a southerly extension of the desert ecosystem of the Wadi Rum World Heritage Site in Jordan.

Harrat Ar Raha

Tertiary and Quaternary basaltic lava fields of north-western Saudi Arabia cover extensive sections of the Arabian Plate. In NEOM, Harrat Ar Raha encroaches on the southeastern-most section, occupying a quite sizeable area of about 1,074 km² in NEOM alone.

Tabuk-Sirhan-Turayf Plain

Along the eastern edge of NEOM the Tabuk sandstones abut the Hisma sandstones and lie underneath the flood basalt lavas of the harrat. They cover roughly 1,536 km² of NEOM. Here sandstone rock pavements—a globally rare ecosystem type found here and in the Hisma desert (Sayre et al. 2014, Brown & Ayasrah 2023)—are interspersed with rocky outcrops, dunes, and broad sand, gravel, and boulder-filled wadis (Al Nafie 1989, Watts & Al Nafie 2003).

Habitat Types

NEOM has identified 103 major terrestrial habitat types and 42 major terrestrial vegetation types (Buro Happold & Brown 2022, Appendix C). Land habitats are diverse, ranging from inland sabkha, gravel plains, and large sand dunes and sheets to rugged granitic peaks, permanent montane seeps, lava plateaus (*harrah*), and reedbeds (Buro Happold & Brown 2022). Changes in ecosystems over distance can be dramatic such that, at times, one can travel from winter snowclad peaks to coral reefs in roughly 40 km (for example, Jibal al Lawz to Gulf of Aqaba).

Based on the results of Buro Happold and Brown (2022) and other studies, dwarf shrubland is the most widespread terrestrial habitat type. Below about 1,200 m, *Haloxylon salicornicum* is by far the most common community with species such as *Artemisia sieberi* and *Tanacetum sinaicum* becoming more prevalent at higher elevations. Other common shrubs and dwarf shrubs include *Retama raetam* and *Zygophyllum molle*. Scattered trees and open woodland occur at all elevations. In the lowlands the dominant species is *Vachellia tortillis* ssp. *tortilis* scattered in plains and foothills or concentrated in wadis or alluvial fans. *Vachellia gerrardi* woodland is typical of higher elevations. Scattered trees occur at higher elevations, including rare and relict species, such as *Prunus korshinskyi*, *Pistacia khinjuk*, *Salix acmophylla*, *Ficus palmata* ssp. *palmata*, and *Juniperus turbinata*. The flora of the higher elevations (generally greater than 1,700 m) is remarkable for assemblages of species that favor cooler and wetter conditions, with high peaks effectively functioning as climatic refugia for numerous species. Coastal vegetation is dominated by halophytic dwarf scrub, such as *Zygophyllum album*, *Limonium axillare*, and *Suaeda vermiculata*. *Tamarix nilotica*, *Halocnemum strobilaceum*, *Juncus rigidus*, and *Aeluropus lagopoides* also occur.

Biogeography

NEOM is located at a crossroads of several biogeographic subregions of the Palearctic realm—Arabian, Mediterranean, Saharan, and Irano-Turanian. Faunal (and floral) elements of each occur together in the NEOM Nature Reserve, creating a rich and distinct terrestrial biota. To illustrate

this crossroads for regional faunas, the chukar partridge (*Alectoris chukar*) occurs in the mountains of northern NEOM and the Hisma Desert while the Arabian partridge (*Alectoris melanocephalus*) occurs in the southern ranges, with a small area of sympatry from Jabal ash Shiyati to Jibal ad Dibbagh and Jabal Shar. Dorcas gazelle (*Gazella d. dorcas*) may have occurred in coastal lowlands of NEOM at the easternmost extension of their range (they occur throughout the Sahara, Sinai, and the Levant) while the Saudi (Dorcas) gazelle (*Gazella d. saudiya*, the *Afri*) likely occurred in the inland sand plains east of the Hejaz Range within NEOM's boundary and similar habitat throughout western Arabia (Morrison-Scott 1939, Lerp et al. 2011, Mallon et al. 2024).

Climate

The climate of NEOM varies considerably between four climatic zones (Vincent 2008) but is generally characterized by low rainfall (0 to 4 mm/year) and high temperatures (~50 °C in the summer) that are typical of hyper-arid, arid, and semi-arid environments, corresponding to extreme desert to semi-desert, respectively (Shmida 1985, Appendix C). The hot season is from June to September with maximum temperatures in July and August. The cooler season is from October to May with minimum temperatures in January. The coastal plains experience the highest temperatures, reaching a maximum of ~50°C in the summer, as well as the lowest annual rainfall, as low as 0 to 4 mm in some areas. By contrast, the monthly average minimum and maximum temperatures of the montane areas of NEOM (the Madyan Range) are no more than 15°C to 25°C. Sub-zero winter temperatures are not uncommon on the highest peaks, such as on the Jibal al Lawz range with the lowest recorded temperature in the past decade reaching -13.9°C (J. Ware *pers. comm.*). Annual rainfall is highest in the mountain ranges and plateau areas to the east, ranging upwards to ~109 mm. Localized rainfall events occur episodically everywhere in NEOM.

Larger Terrestrial Vertebrate Surveys

Information on larger terrestrial vertebrates in NEOM Nature Reserve is derived from review of published literature and prior NEOM survey reports, baited and unbaited camera-trap surveys, direct observation of individuals of the species, or other credible evidence, such as recent horns of ibex or clearly identifiable scat (for example, striped hyena, Indian crested porcupine), or eDNA or DNA from samples. Footprints were not considered adequate evidence.

Nature Reserve Camera-Trap Survey Sites

Nature Reserve camera-trap surveys (which include NEOM Environment and KAUST-BDC surveys) were carried out in 248 localities (Fig. 2, Appendix A) throughout NEOM from 2019 to 2024 with 199 cameras retrieved and 49 lost or compromised. An additional 232 cameras were deployed by NEOM development sectors that provided presence data for several target species (specifically, Arabian wolf, sand cat, striped hyena, honey badger, Blanford's fox, Rüppell's fox, Arabian red fox, camel, sheep, goat, domestic dog, domestic cat) (Appendix A). Thirty-eight new localities were surveyed by Nature Reserve in 2025-2026 for presence data (Appendix A). No survey data from NEOM's islands is included here.

Nature Reserve camera traps were deployed at sites throughout NEOM that were generally representative of major ecosystems and landforms (Fig. 2). Though many camera traps were sited in more remote locations to increase chances of detection of more sensitive or rare wildlife species, such as larger predators, several cameras were placed at sites where human activity was high. Even some cameras placed on the highest, most remote peaks were disturbed by people, likely hunters. Several cameras were deployed in NEOM long-term ecological monitoring sites (Fig. 3).

NEOM development sectors shared presence data for 232 camera-trap localities surveyed from 2021 through 2024, primarily in the coastal lowlands, central Hejaz Range wadis, southern Hisma Desert, and harrat (Fig. 2, Appendix A). These surveys used baited (that is, water, sardines) and unbaited camera traps. This presence data was not used to estimate diel activity or detection rates for the target species or activities in this analysis.

Nubian ibex

Figure 2. (a) NEOM Nature Reserve, KAUST-BDC, NEOM Environment (darker green dots) (2019 through early 2024), (b) NEOM development sector (2021 through 2024, blue dots), and (c) NEOM Nature Reserve additional (lighter green dots) camera-trap survey (late 2024 to early 2026) localities. Light blue dots are 'lost' or compromised camera traps with no data retrieved. Refer to Appendix A for camera-trap coordinates.

Figure 3. KAUST-BDC survey camera-trap localities in NEOM Nature Reserve Long-Term Ecological Monitoring Sites 2023-2024 (blue and green grid squares). Priority sites (yellow circles) are for a different study.

Confident Observations

Where credible detections or observations of wildlife species apart from the camera-trap surveys were available, these were added to the presence maps for a subset of rarer species, specifically striped hyena, caracal, Blanford's fox, Rüppell's fox, sand cat, honey badger, Indian crested porcupine, Nubian ibex, and Arabian wolf. These 'other detections' are from field observations of NEOM Nature Reserve wildlife specialists and observation data from selected published and unpublished surveys (for example, Aloufi & Amr 2018, Clarke & Smithson 2018, Al Ahmari et al. 2024, Campbell et al. 2024; Appendix B)

Survey design & camera deployment

This larger terrestrial fauna assessment is not derived from a single, systematic larger terrestrial wildlife survey employing camera traps. Rather, this baseline report is a compilation of several sources of information. This includes data from 199 camera trap survey efforts that were deployed over the course of 5 years (2019 to 2024) across NEOM and presence data from an additional 248 camera-traps deployed by NEOM development sectors (2021-2024). These surveys were carried

out for a variety of purposes, including: (1) rapid assessments of the presence and abundance of wildlife species and human activities in localities around NEOM; (2) relatively remote areas targeted for surveying for larger and rarer species of wildlife, some possibly extirpated; (3) establishing wildlife baselines for ESIA (that is, Environmental and Social Impact Assessment for possible development projects) and greening and rewilding initiative project sites; and (4) part of a program of long-term ecological monitoring (LTEM) at permanent LTEM sites around the NEOM Nature Reserve. Thus, the camera-trap deployment approach was more opportunistic and focused on a subset of possible development areas (to assess potential impacts and mitigations) and representative and remote areas (to assess the ‘status’ of wildlife) rather than a coordinated, systematic survey design. There was a different number of ‘active in the field’ cameras each year, with the greatest number being active in 2023 (Table 1).

Table 1. Number of Nature Reserve and NEOM development sector (NDS) survey camera traps active in the field by year between 2019 and 2024. Note, some camera traps were continuously deployed over multiple years at the same locality. Some localities had two cameras surveying different views.

Year	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
# NR cameras active	1	24	62	16	103	36
# NDS - cameras active	-	15	19	79	119	

The length of time an individual camera trap was active varied considerably among cameras, from weeks to years. We tried, where possible, to have camera traps operating for at least 5 months, a period recommended by the Panthera team working with the Global Fund for the Arabian Leopard (<https://panthera.org/arabian-leopard-initiative>) who have conducted camera trap surveys for Arabian leopards throughout the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (Panthera survey team, pers. comm. 2023). Rarefaction analyses suggest this period was adequate for detecting a most of the extant larger terrestrial vertebrate fauna (see Chao et al. 2014). O’Brien et al. (2003) recommend leaving cameras in the field for 100 trap night to give a satisfactory level of detectability for a good proportion of the fauna, though this recommendation was for tropical forest faunas, not those of hyper-arid ecosystems. The NDS camera-traps were deployed for a few weeks up to 3 months. Cameras were operating during both the cool and hot seasons.

Wiejerman et al. (2024) found that 63 camera-traps deployed for 1.5 years across a xeric protected area (approximately 3,600 km² in central Saudi Arabia) was adequate to sample 90% of the terrestrial fauna. The 433 camera-traps from which data was obtained in NEOM exceed that number considerably.

The camera trap placement in local environments also varied. Only in a few localities did cameras follow the one to two km spacing normally recommended for mammal community surveys (Amin et al. 2015). Some cameras were placed on trees with cables, some hidden in rocks, and some were camouflaged with ghillie-suit strings (Fig. 4). The ghillie camouflage seemed to work well to hide the camera from people but, during the spring, birds would pull at the string for nesting material and threads would obscure the view or would cause the cameras to trigger causing SD cards to become full quickly. Twisting the string on double stick tape and trimming around the sensors and lenses helped but we abandoned the practice eventually.

Figure 4. Camera-trap with ghillie-string camouflage attached.

Different people with different levels of camera-trapping knowledge and skills deployed the cameras. Some cameras were placed low to the ground, some higher up in rocks or trees, and the camera aspect was not standardized. There was no standard placement of cameras other than placing them in locations that seemed favorable for detecting wildlife (for example, higher elevations or near hot season water pools or along game trails) or that were well hidden to avoid losing the cameras. In general, a single camera-trap was placed at a height of 30-45 cm positioned either perpendicular or at a 45° angle to game trails and pathways likely to be used by mammals

at a distance of *c.* 4-8 m to maximize detection probability and with the aim of obtaining full body lateral images. Where possible, we avoided pointing cameras at the rising and setting sun and full sun towards the south. Camera installation protocol should require each camera to be triggered by a field technician holding a whiteboard with location ID, date and time upon activation and deactivation to verify camera function. However, this protocol was not followed for all camera placements.

Despite the considerable variation in the specifics of individual camera trap deployments and other shortcomings of the survey design, the large number of localities sampled (199 [+232 from NDS surveys], and 38 post-2024 new localities by NEOM Nature Reserve, to date) and images gathered (400,000+), 10,000+ detections of target species and activities, the 28,000+ trap nights, and the broad geographic and ecological distribution of these combined camera trap deployments helps lend confidence to emergent patterns of wildlife distribution and behavior. At a minimum, detection of wildlife species at different localities constitutes robust ‘presence’ data.

In the Nature Reserve survey efforts, the same brand of camera trap was used (Browning) with similar settings (Table 2). The cameras used an infrared flash, which minimized the risk of startling animals in low light or at night as would be the case with white flash, thereby influencing future detections if animals avoided flash areas. White flash would also increase detection by people at night who might damage the cameras (for example, hunters). Roughly a third (36%) of the camera traps used water and sardine baits (the KAUST-BDC and NDS surveys).

Table 2. Camera-trap Settings for NEOM Nature Reserve and KAUST-BDC surveys.

	NEOM Nature Reserve Surveys: Browning Trail Camera HD ProX Model: BTC-SHDPX	KAUST/BDC Surveys: Browning Trail Camera Dark Ops Pro DCL
Image Resolution	Ultra (20 MP)	26 MP
Mode	Photos	Photos
Capture Photos per Event (Number)	STD-3 Shot	3 multi-shot photos per trigger
Trigger Speed	0.22	0.15
Photo Delay	1 minute	10 minutes
Camera Mode	Trail - 24 hours/continuous operation/IR Night Illumination (36m flash range)	Trail - 24 hours/continuous operation/IR Night Illumination (30m flash range)
Night Exposure	Fast motion	-
Flash type	Smart IR on; red glow IR	Invisible night IR illumination
SD Card Capacity	64 GB	64 GB

Deployment details in the four survey efforts are as follows:

1. *NEOM Nature Reserve Surveys (2019-2024)* – NEOM Nature Reserve deployed 248 Browning Trail Cameras (HD ProX Model: BTC-SHDPX) from 2019 to 2024. The sites sampled occur throughout NEOM, with an emphasis on representative, rugged, and remote areas. Cameras were initially cabled to trees or placed on rocks. However, high loss and

damage rates of camera traps led surveyors in 2023 and 2024 to try camouflaging camera traps with ghillie-suit hairs and hidden in rocks (no cables) (Fig. 4). No baits were used. Data was obtained from 199 cameras, the data from the remaining cameras was lost (for example, camera stolen or destroyed, camera malfunction). NEOM Nature Reserve deployed camera-traps at 38 new localities in 2025-2026 and the species detections are included in this update. These 38 cameras were baited with sardines.

2. *NEOM Environment Science & Technology Survey (2024)* – Seven Browning trail cameras (model not known) were deployed by NEOM Environment Science & Technology in early 2024 at higher elevations around Jibal al Lawz. These cameras are included in the 248 Nature Reserve camera count. The camera model and specifications were not available, though IR (infrared) images were taken, and no white flash images are evident. Most of the cameras were placed on rocks or near the ground. These camera traps were not camouflaged or baited.
3. *KAUST-BDC Surveys (2023, 2024)* – Seventy-eight cameras were deployed by KAUST-BDC for wildlife surveys and long-term ecological monitoring baselines. These cameras are included in the 248 Nature Reserve camera count. Each camera, Browning Dark Ops Pro DCL®, was installed approximately 0.5-1 m above the ground and secured in a metal security box with a cable lock to a tree or built into rock formations. These camera traps were not camouflaged. Bait, tinned sardines or tuna, was placed in front of each camera on the ground to attract animals into the field of view. To enhance the likelihood of capturing fauna on camera, the devices were strategically positioned in areas anticipated to animal activity, including frequently utilized wildlife trails. Throughout the fieldwork, the team utilized ArcGIS Survey123 to document essential information. This encompassed recording camera trap coordinates, noting the time, date, and support structure for each camera trap deployment, documenting camera settings during installation, capturing photographic records of locations for future reference.
4. *NEOM Development Sector Surveys (2021-2024)* – Wildlife surveys carried out by NEOM development sectors resulted in detections of several rare to uncommon species, including sand cat, Ruppel's fox, Arabian wolf, striped hyena, and honey badger. These localities are included in the distribution maps for these species. These surveys deployed 91 baited (that is, water, sardines) and unbaited camera traps. For these cameras, we only obtained presence data, so data from these cameras were not used to estimate diel activity or detection rates. These cameras are not included in the 248 Nature Reserve camera count. For these surveys, only detection events for a subset of target species were evaluated, not entire datasets.

Lessons learned from camera-trap surveys form the basis of recommended future deployment protocols in Box 1.

Box 1 – *NEOM Nature Reserve recommended camera-trap protocols for camera placement and configuration for future surveys:*

- Cameras placed at a height of 30-45 cm on a tree or on rocks to ensure smaller fauna are detected (lower portions of larger species are relatively easy to identify to species)
- Ensure the horizon is in the upper half of the image
- The minimum distance for clearing of vegetation in front of camera is 4 m, the aim being to make sure that a small animal, such as a cat, would be visible 2 m in front of the camera, vegetation grows up quickly in the cool season
- Check that movement of existing plants in front of the camera will not cause false triggers
- Do not face towards rising or setting sun, where possible
- Face cameras perpendicular to game trails, where possible
- Ensure the camera is not pointing too far upwards to have debris or water block camera lens or IR trigger
- Cameras should not be placed such that rock faces are to the side or level with lens as at night the illumination of rocks will blind the image, close vegetation can also blind night images.
- Cameras should not be placed low in wadis (canyons or gullies) where flash floods can occur or on rock faces that likely have heavy cascades of rainfall runoff
- Cameras are set to take three pictures per trigger with a one to two second delay, a 0.2 trigger delay, and a minimum detection range of 25 m
- Infrared flash is used for night images (note, black flash cameras that do not have an initial red light showing produce inferior images)
- Cameras camouflaged with ghillie suit string, twisted and applied with doublestick tape tend to have a lower loss rate, however, strings loosened by the wind and nesting birds can interfere with camera operations, it is not recommended to use this camouflage in the future.
- Cameras are not cable locked but well hidden in rocks
- A minimum of 64 GB memory card is used
- Non-rechargeable batteries are best, Duracell AA or Energizer AA Ultimate Lithium batteries are particularly good, note that locally sourced, off-market batteries often fail, some batteries lasted more than two years
- Each camera is left out for 150 trap nights at a minimum
- Camera trap surveys are done in the hot and cool season, if possible
- Camera trap surveys conducted as part of long-term monitoring programs must use the same protocol and should strive to sample during the hot and cool season.

NEOM Biodiversity Surveys

We reviewed and evaluated biodiversity surveys carried out for NEOM since 2018 (Appendix B) for evidence of detections of target species. These surveys reported species detected through diverse methods, such as direct observation, spoor, scat, horns, DNA, eDNA, camera-trap detections, acoustic surveys, and other methods. We did not consider spoor (footprint) as confident evidence for occurrence.

Survey Faunal Target Species

The survey's target list of species reflects an estimated 'intact' larger terrestrial vertebrate fauna for the NEOM Nature Reserve that existed roughly 100+ years ago (Table 4). We did not record data on larger predatory birds, such as owls, ravens, hawks, or eagles, as these are not well surveyed using camera-traps. We did not record vultures as they are not efficiently surveyed using unbaited camera traps. Vultures are present—since 2021, for example, one major ornithological survey by NEOM observed 150 griffon, 310 Egyptian, and one cinereous vulture in one autumn—but rarely detected through unbaited camera traps. One viverrid, *Herpestes ichneumon*, and one mustelid, *Vormela peregusna*, have IUCN Red List distributions adjacent to NEOM in Jordan, Israel, and the Sinai Peninsula, Egypt (Abramov et al. 2016, Do Linh San et al. 2016). These two species are not on the target list as there are no records of the ichneumon in northwest Saudi Arabia and only one record of the marbled polecat (*V. peregusna*) in the far north of Saudi Arabia (Nadir 1991). However, there is an anecdotal report from 2022 from a naturalist in NEOM who spotted mongoose-like animals crossing a road in northern NEOM. European brown hare (*Lepus europaeus*) occurs on some faunal lists of possible species for the region, but this survey considers NEOM Nature Reserve to be out of its natural range. The brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) is, surprisingly, listed as historically present in the Sinai of Egypt, an area geographically adjacent to NEOM, but now considered Regionally Extinct (McLellan et al. 2017). However, there was no evidence of historical or recent occurrences of this species located for the NEOM area.

Arabian wolf

Table 3. Survey faunal target species of larger terrestrial vertebrates (38 species): yellow shading denotes domesticated or feral species (7 species); red shading denotes extinct / extirpated species, including those that can be reintroduced or for which counterpart species (or subspecies) may be rewilded or species that possibly occurred here in the recent past. Five target human activities are also listed.

Family	Common Name	Species	Status & Comments
Bovidae	Domestic Goat	<i>Capra hircus</i>	domesticated
Bovidae	Nubian ibex	<i>Capra nubiana</i>	extant and rewilding releases
Bovidae	Arabian gazelle	<i>Gazella arabica</i>	<i>Idmi</i> , possibly extant and reintroduced recently
Bovidae	Dorcas gazelle	<i>Gazella dorcas</i>	possibly extant or extirpated in NEOM
Bovidae	Sand gazelle	<i>Gazella marica</i>	<i>Reem</i> , extirpated and reintroduced recently
Bovidae	Arabian Dorcas gazelle	<i>Gazella saudiya</i>	<i>Afri</i> , extinct
Bovidae	Arabian oryx	<i>Oryx leucoryx</i>	extirpated and recently reintroduced
Bovidae	Sheep	<i>Ovis aries</i>	domesticated
Bovidae	Lesser kudu	<i>Tragelaphus imberbis</i>	possibly once occurred in Arabian Peninsula
Camelidae	Camel	<i>Camelus dromedarius</i>	domestic or feral
Canidae	Asian jackal	<i>Canis aureus</i>	
Canidae	Domestic dog	<i>Canis familiaris</i>	domestic and feral
Canidae	Arabian wolf	<i>Canis lupus arabs</i>	
Canidae	Blanford's fox	<i>Vulpes cana</i>	
Canidae	Rüppell's fox	<i>Vulpes rueppelli</i>	
Canidae	Arabian red fox	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	
Equidae	Donkey	<i>Equus africanus asinus</i>	domestic and feral
Equidae	Domestic horse	<i>Equus caballus</i>	domestic, present in NEOM
Equidae	Onager	<i>Equus hemionus</i>	Native Syrian Onager subspecies <i>Equus hemionus hemmipe</i> is Extinct, rewilding counterpart species for Syrian onager
Erinaceidae	Desert hedgehog	<i>Paraechinus aethiopicus</i>	
Felidae	Cheetah	<i>Acinoyx jubatus</i> (Arabian form)	Arabian cheetah form is extinct
Felidae	Caracal	<i>Caracal caracal schmitzi</i>	
Felidae	Domestic cat	<i>Felis catus</i>	domestic and feral
Felidae	Sand cat	<i>Felis margarita</i>	
Felidae	Arabian wild cat	<i>Felis lybica lybica</i>	
Felidae	Lion	<i>Panthera leo</i>	extirpated, Arabian subspecies unknown
Felidae	Arabian leopard	<i>Panthera pardus nimr</i>	possibly extant or extirpated in NEOM
Hyaenidae	Striped hyaena	<i>Hyaena hyaena</i>	
Hystriidae	Indian crested porcupine	<i>Hystrix indica</i>	
Leporidae	Cape hare	<i>Lepus capensis arabicus</i>	
Mustellidae	Honey badger or ratel	<i>Mellivora capensis pumilio</i>	
Procaviidae	Rock hyrax	<i>Procavia capensis</i>	
Agamidae	Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard	<i>Uromastix aegyptica</i>	
Varanidae	Desert monitor	<i>Varanus griseus</i>	
Phasianidae	Chukar partridge	<i>Alectoris chukar</i>	
Phasianidae	Arabian partridge	<i>Alectoris melanocephala</i>	

Phasianidae	Sand partridge	<i>Ammoperdix heyi</i>	
Struthionidae	Red-necked ostrich	<i>Struthio camelus camelus</i>	Native Arabian ostrich subspecies, <i>Struthio camelus syriacus</i> , is Extinct, <i>S. c. camelus</i> is a rewilding counterpart subspecies, reintroduced
Human Activity Targets			
livestock herder			Human activity target
hunter			Human activity target
wood/plant collector			Human activity target
hiker			Human activity target
vehicle			Human activity target

Survey Human Activity Targets

In addition to wildlife species, the survey recorded detections on the humans engaged in different activities that may potentially have an impact on larger terrestrial vertebrates (Table 3):

- Livestock herder – individuals closely associated with livestock or in a vehicle around livestock
- Hunter – individuals with binoculars, rifles, camouflage or other hunting gear
- Wood/plant collector – individuals with live or dead plant material in their arms, hands, or backpacks and not clearly associated with livestock (livestock herders will collect plants and woods while tending livestock)
- Hiker – people not clearly associated with livestock herding, hunting, or wood/plant collecting
- Driving – vehicle of any type.

Arabian wild cat

Ecological Guild of Target Species

Different species targets in Table 4 are assigned ecological guilds as categorized in Table 5.

Table 4. Ecological guilds of different target species for this survey.

Family	Common Name	Species	Ecological Guild
Bovidae	Domestic Goat	<i>Capra hircus</i>	5
Bovidae	Nubian ibex	<i>Capra nubiana</i>	4
Bovidae	Arabian gazelle	<i>Gazella arabica</i>	5
Bovidae	Dorcas gazelle	<i>Gazella dorcas</i>	5
Bovidae	Sand gazelle	<i>Gazella marica</i>	5
Bovidae	Arabian Dorcas gazelle	<i>Gazella saudiya</i>	5
Bovidae	Arabian oryx	<i>Oryx leucoryx</i>	4
Bovidae	Sheep	<i>Ovis aries</i>	5
Bovidae	Lesser kudu	<i>Tragelaphus imberbis</i>	4
Camelidae	Camel	<i>Camelus dromedarius</i>	4
Canidae	Asian jackal	<i>Canis aureus</i>	2
Canidae	Domestic dog	<i>Canis familiaris</i>	1
Canidae	Arabian wolf	<i>Canis lupus arabs</i>	1
Canidae	Blanford's fox	<i>Vulpes cana</i>	2
Canidae	Rüppell's fox	<i>Vulpes rueppelli</i>	2
Canidae	Arabian red fox	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	2
Equidae	Donkey	<i>Equus africanus asinus</i>	4
Equidae	Domestic horse	<i>Equus caballus</i>	4
Equidae	Onager	<i>Equus hemionus x kulan</i>	4
Erinaceidae	Desert hedgehog	<i>Paraechinus aethiopicus</i>	3
Felidae	Cheetah	<i>Acinoyx jubatus</i>	1
Felidae	Caracal	<i>Caracal caracal schmitzi</i>	1
Felidae	Domestic cat	<i>Felis catus</i>	2
Felidae	Sand Cat	<i>Felis margarita</i>	2
Felidae	Arabian wild cat	<i>Felis lybica lybica</i>	2
Felidae	Lion	<i>Panthera leo</i>	1
Felidae	Arabian leopard	<i>Panthera pardus nimr</i>	1
Hyaenidae	Striped hyaena	<i>Hyaena hyaena</i>	1
Hystriidae	Indian crested porcupine	<i>Hystrix indica</i>	5
Leporidae	Cape hare	<i>Lepus capensis arabicus</i>	6
Mustellidae	Honey badger or ratel	<i>Mellivora capensis pumilio</i>	1
Procaviidae	Rock hyrax	<i>Procavia capensis</i>	6
Agamidae	Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard	<i>Uromastyx aegyptica</i>	6
Varanidae	Desert monitor	<i>Varanus griseus</i>	2
Phasianidae	Chukar partridge	<i>Alectoris chukar</i>	6
Phasianidae	Arabian partridge	<i>Alectoris melanocephala</i>	6
Phasianidae	Sand partridge	<i>Ammoperdix heyi</i>	6
Struthionidae	Red-necked ostrich	<i>Struthio camelus camelus</i>	4

Table 5. *Ecological guild of target larger terrestrial vertebrate species in NEOM Nature Reserve.*

1. Larger-sized carnivores

Lion – extinct; Arabian leopard – extirpated; Cheetah – extinct; Arabian wolf; Domestic dog; Ratel or honey badger, Caracal; Striped hyena

2. Medium-sized carnivores/omnivores

Sand cat; Wildcat; Domestic cat; Arabian red fox; Blanford's fox; Rüppell's fox; Golden jackal; Pharaoh eagle owl, desert monitor

3. Smaller carnivores/omnivores

Hedgehog; Tawny owl; Houbara bustard, ichneumon

4. Larger-sized herbivores

Arabian oryx – reintroduced; Nubian ibex; Onager – extinct, counterpart rewild candidate; Donkey – feral and domestic; Domestic horse; Camel; Red-necked ostrich – Arabian ostrich extinct, counterpart rewilded

5. Medium-sized herbivores

Dorcas gazelle – possibly extirpated; Saudi Dorcas gazelle – extinct; Arabian gazelle; Sand gazelle; Sheep; Goat

6. Smaller-sized herbivores

Cape hare; Arabian partridge; Chukar partridge; Sand partridge; Spiny-tailed lizard; Houbara bustard

7. Larger scavengers

Griffon vulture; Cinereous vulture; Egyptian vulture; Lammergeier – possibly extirpated; striped hyena

Other Smaller Terrestrial Vertebrate and Arboreal Guilds

8. Medium-sized Scavengers/Omnivores

Fan-tailed raven; Brown-necked raven

9. Bipedal rodent granivores

10. Quadrupedal rodent granivores

11. Small cursorial mammalian insectivores

12. Small arboreal mammalian insectivores

13. Myrmecophagous (ant eating) reptile

14. Open space, long-legged lizard

15. Medium-sized, lizard-eating lizard

16. Insectivorous birds

17. Granivorous birds

Data Analysis

Sets of camera-trap images from the same locality and with continuous dates were considered a single sampling event.

Cameras

For each camera trap, the following features were recorded:

- Camera number
- General location
- Coordinates in decimal degrees
- Elevation in meters
- Date of deployment
- Last date active in the field
- Trap nights active
- Major ecosystem type
- Landform

Targets

For each target, the following features were derived from an image on which they are detected:

- Camera-trap location of detection
- Date of detection
- Time of detection.

Dataset

From the entire Nature Reserve survey data set and for each target type, the following features were derived:

- Locations where detected (NDS Survey data only for a selected subset of taxa)
- Detection rates (detections per 100 trap nights with one detection every 30 minutes, see below) (Nature Reserve survey data only was used)
- Seasonality of detections, that is, hot or cool season (June 1 to September 30 is hot season and October 1 to May 31 is cool season) (Nature Reserve survey data only was used)
- Diel activity for different target species or activities (Nature Reserve survey data only was used)
- In some cases, temporal and spatial correlates are evaluated, in some cases, such as proximity to roads, presence of hunters, herders, hikers, major ecosystem type, landform, season, time of day

Analyzing Images

For each Nature Reserve sampling event, that is a set of images from a single camera at a single locality operating for a continuous period of time, we went through all the images and recorded each time a target was detected and the date and time of that detection. For NDS surveys and for

each camera, a subset of target species (that is, Arabian wolf, Blanford's fox, Rüppell's fox, sand cat, striped hyena, Arabian wild cat, Arabian red fox, honey badger, desert hedgehog, camel, goat, sheep, domestic dog, domestic cat) had detections, time, and date recorded. The NDS survey data was only used for assessing presence for the subset of target taxa (see above), not diel activity or detection rates.

Species 'trapping' or detection rates were calculated as the mean number of independent photographic 'events' per trap night x 100. An 'event' was defined as any sequence of images for a given species occurring after an interval of >30 min from the end of the previous three-image sequence of that species (Tobler et al. 2008). Standard errors are calculated from the standard deviation of the daily trapping rate. Trapping (detection) rate provides a simple index of relative abundance (RAI) with the assumption that a target species will trigger cameras in relation to their density, all other factors being equal. If a standardized protocol is used for the surveys, including consistent positioning and management of cameras to ensure detection probabilities are similar, then trapping rates provide a comparative index within species, but are not generally suitable for comparisons between species. Given the variation in camera deployment approach and lengths of time deployed, trapping rate is challenging to estimate for species and activities in this survey. However, we calculated a range of detection rates based on the full set of sampling events for each target and then divided this into quartiles to be able to present a relative level of 'presence' or 'activity' of each species or human activity in different grid cells. We averaged camera detection rates within each grid cell and used these averages to estimate the range of detection rates and break into six ranges of detection rate with a range tailored to each species and activity.

We did not collect data on group size, age, sex, or behavior (with a few exceptions) from the images (Amin et al. 2016). We did not analyze occupancy as the camera-trap sampling approach was not standardized and required assumptions were not met.

Circadian (24 hour) species or human activity patterns were constructed by tallying the number of events per hour (all events, not just the hourly event used for detection rate calculations) across each survey time period. To assess seasonal patterns, we identify which season each detection occurred for a subset of target species or activities, namely Arabian wolf, sheep, goat, camel, donkey, chukar partridge, Arabian partridge, sand partridge, livestock herder, Blanford's fox, Nubian ibex, and hunters. In general, June 1 to September 30 is the hot (hotter) season and October 1 to May 31 is the cool (cooler) season.

Arabian wolf, Jibal ad Dibbagh

Jebel al Lawz

RESULTS

Camera-Trap Survey Effort

For the Nature Reserve camera-trap effort (includes the KAUST-BDC, NEOM Environment Science & Technology surveys), the following metrics are estimated (note, this does not include data from the NDS camera-trap surveys or additional 2025-2026 camera-trap deployments):

- Total number of distinct camera survey events defined as a continuously active camera with a unique view of a locality: 248 camera-trap survey events. Of these 199 camera traps were retrieved, 49 were lost (that is, entirely gone or washed away by flood) or compromised (for example, damaged, SD card or batteries stolen, crushed and thrown in a rock pool, burned in a fire, lens and sensors taped over or damaged, camera pointed to ground or sky).
- Total number of cameras where data was lost is a loss rate not unexpected for a region with a lot of human activity, challenges in hiding cameras in the landscape (for example, trees may be uncommon, cameras are easily detected on trees), and only a few cameras placed in truly remote areas. Even cameras placed at high peaks were commonly tampered with by people, likely hunters.
- Total number of trap nights cameras were deployed: 28,813 trap nights.
- Total number of wildlife and human activity events: 62,733 events.
- Total number of images: estimated 448,611 images.

Target Species Detected

The larger terrestrial vertebrate species detected by this survey and review of other NEOM biodiversity surveys are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Larger terrestrial vertebrate species detected in NEOM from 2019-2024 (26 species).

Family	Common Name	Species Name	Status & Comments
Bovidae	Domestic Goat	<i>Capra hircus</i>	domesticated
Bovidae	Nubian ibex	<i>Capra nubiana</i>	extant and rewilding releases
Bovidae	Arabian gazelle	<i>Gazella arabica</i>	<i>Idmi</i> , possibly extant and reintroduced recently, single female detected may be farm escapee
Bovidae	Sand gazelle	<i>Gazella marica</i>	reintroduced into two rewilding areas
Bovidae	Sheep	<i>Ovis aries</i>	domesticated
Camelidae	Camel	<i>Camelus dromedarius</i>	domesticated or feral
Canidae	Domestic dog	<i>Canis familiaris</i>	domesticated or feral
Canidae	Arabian wolf	<i>Canis lupu sarabs</i>	some wolf-dog hybrids observed
Canidae	Blanford's fox	<i>Vulpes cana</i>	
Canidae	Rüppell's fox	<i>Vulpes rueppelli</i>	
Canidae	Arabian red fox	<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	

Equidae	Donkey	<i>Equus africanus asinus</i>	domestic and feral
Erinaceidae	Desert hedgehog	<i>Paraechinus aethiopicus</i>	
Felidae	Caracal	<i>Caracal caracal schmitzi</i>	2 caracal scat detections only (Clarke & Smithson 2018, Campbell et al. 2024), anecdotal reports
Felidae	Domestic cat	<i>Felis catus</i>	domestic and feral
Felidae	Sand cat	<i>Felis margarita</i>	
Felidae	Arabian wild cat	<i>Felis lybica lybica</i>	
Hyaenidae	Striped hyena	<i>Hyaena hyaena</i>	
Leporidae	Cape hare	<i>Lepus capensis arabicus</i>	
Mustellidae	Honey badger or ratel	<i>Mellivora capensis</i>	
Procaviidae	Rock hyrax	<i>Procavia capensis</i>	
Agamidae	Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard	<i>Uromastyx aegyptica</i>	
Varanidae	Desert monitor	<i>Varanus griseus</i>	
Phasianidae	Chukar partridge	<i>Alectoris chukar</i>	
Phasianidae	Arabian partridge	<i>Alectoris melanocephala</i>	
Phasianidae	Sand partridge	<i>Ammoperdix heyi</i>	

Target Species Not Detected

Target species not detected in this survey are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Larger terrestrial vertebrate species that are expected or once occurred in the sample zone according to available distribution maps and literature but not detected by this survey (13 species). Red shading indicates species that would not be expected to be detected as they are either confidently extinct or extirpated. Sand gazelle, Arabian oryx, Nubian ibex, Arabian gazelle, and red-necked ostrich have recently been rewilded to two sites in NEOM Nature Reserve.

Family	Common Name	Species Name	Status & Comments
Bovidae	Dorcas gazelle	<i>Gazella dorcas</i>	Possibly extant or extirpated in NEOM
Bovidae	Sand gazelle (wild)	<i>Gazella marica</i>	Reem, extirpated and reintroduced recently into rewilding zone, detected in a rewilding area during survey
Bovidae	Arabian Dorcas gazelle	<i>Gazella saudiya</i>	Afri, extinct
Bovidae	Arabian oryx	<i>Oryx leucoryx</i>	Extirpated and recently reintroduced into rewilding zone
Bovidae	Lesser kudu	<i>Tragelaphus imberbis</i>	Possibly once occurred in Arabian Peninsula, possible petroglyph of kudu in Al Suru foothills
Canidae	Golden jackal	<i>Canis aureus</i>	Recently recorded in Prince Mohammed bin Salman Royal Reserve (PMBSRR) just south of NEOM
Equidae	Domestic horse	<i>Equus caballus</i>	Domestic horse not detected by camera-traps
Equidae	Onager	<i>Equus hemionus x kulan</i>	Native Syrian Onager subspecies <i>Equus hemionus hemmipe</i> is Extinct, rewilding counterpart species for Syrian onager
Felidae	Cheetah	<i>Acinoyx jubatus</i>	Native Arabian cheetah subspecies is extinct

Felidae	Lion	<i>Panthera leo</i>	Extirpated, unknown if subspecies
Felidae	Arabian leopard	<i>Panthera pardus nimr</i>	Possibly extant or extirpated in NEOM
Hystricidae	Indian crested porcupine	<i>Hystrix indica</i>	a possible single scat by Clarke & Smithson (2018) but no clear identification
Struthionidae	Red-necked ostrich	<i>Struthio camelus camelus</i>	Native Arabian ostrich subspecies, <i>Struthio camelus syriacus</i> , is Extinct, <i>S. c. camelus</i> is a rewilding counterpart subspecies, introduced into rewilding zones

Number of Sites Detected & Number of Detection Events for Species and Activity Targets

Arabian red fox, camel, sand partridge, and domestic goat were highest for both number of sites detected and number of detection events, with Arabian red fox and camel being the first and second highest, respectively (Tables 8, 9). Honey badger and Arabian gazelle had the two lowest number of detection sites and detection events. The Line survey similarly detected Arabian red fox most frequently, though livestock was detected less commonly (Table 10). The reason for this is unclear, but it may be because The Line survey cameras typically ran only one to two weeks (up to 3 months maximum) or the cameras were placed in more difficult or remote terrain to focus on wildlife detections. The Line survey cameras had several detections of rare species, such as Rüppell's fox, sand cat, honey badger, and striped hyena, perhaps due to attracting them more through consistent baiting with water and sardines, or, in the case of sand cat and Rüppell's fox, having several cameras placed in favorable lowland sand plain habitat. All the larger wildlife species detected by The Line survey were detected in the Nature Reserve survey, as well (Tables 8-10).

Arabian red fox

Table 8. Total sites and total detection events for each species and activity survey target, ordered by highest to lowest detection events. These are for Nature Reserve camera-trap surveys only.

Species & Activity Target	Total Sites Detected	Total Detection Events
Arabian red fox	142	2340
Camel	104	1573
Domestic goat	90	1299
Sand partridge	92	1220
Hiker	68	688
Arabian wolf	61	414
Livestock herder	71	390
Sheep	59	367
Vehicle	34	330
Domestic dog	46	267
Nubian ibex	29	245
Arabian wild cat	63	244
Desert hedgehog	36	213
Cape hare	9	118
Arabian partridge	4	102
Blanford's fox	28	100
Chukar partridge	26	99
E spiny-tailed lizard	4	71
Hunter	16	69
Donkey	20	58
Rock hyrax	12	52
Plant collector	16	30
Domestic cat	7	21
Sand gazelle	1	18
Rüppell's fox	7	10
Desert monitor	4	8
Striped hyaena	3	5
Honey badger or Ratel	1	2
Sand cat	2	2
Arabian gazelle	1	1

Table 9. Total sites and total detection events for each species and activity survey target, ordered from highest to lowest number of sites detected. These are for Nature Reserve camera-trap surveys only.

Species & Activity Target	Total Sites Detected	Total Detection Events
Arabian red fox	142	2340
Camel	104	1573
Sand partridge	92	1220
Domestic goat	90	1299
Livestock herder	71	390
Hiker	68	688
Arabian wild cat	63	244
Arabian wolf	61	414
Sheep	59	367
Domestic dog	46	267
Desert hedgehog	36	213
Vehicle	34	330
Nubian ibex	29	245
Blanford's fox	28	100
Chukar partridge	26	99
Donkey	20	58
Hunter	16	69
Plant collector	16	30
Rock hyrax	12	52
Cape hare	9	118
Domestic cat	7	21
Rüppell's fox	7	10
Arabian partridge	4	102
E spiny-tailed lizard	4	71
Desert monitor	4	8
Striped hyaena	3	5
Sand cat	2	2
Sand gazelle	1	18
Honey badger or Ratel	1	2
Arabian gazelle	1	1

Table 10. *The NDS survey camera-trap detections of targets from entire 2021 to 2024 dataset.*

Target Species	# Detection Events
Red fox (Arabian red fox)	788
Desert hedgehog	111
Blanford's fox	53
Wildcat (Arabian wildcat)	41
Grey wolf (Arabian wolf)	30
Feral dog	18
Rüppell's fox	16
Domestic camel	14
Domestic goat	8
Sand cat	7
Striped hyaena	6
Feral cat	5
Cape hare	3
Honey badger	2
Domestic sheep	1

Species Richness

This camera-trap survey and review of other NEOM biodiversity surveys report detections of 26 species of the target list of 38 larger terrestrial vertebrates in NEOM Nature Reserve between 2018 and 2024 (Table 6). Thirteen species on the target list were not detected, nine of which would not be expected to be detected as they are confidently considered to be either extinct or extirpated (Table 7). Nine species or subspecies on the target list are considered Extinct (Arabian cheetah, Syrian ass [onager], Arabian [Syrian] ostrich, Saudi Dorcas gazelle, Asiatic lion, Arabian form lesser kudu [if it was present in the past]) or extirpated (Arabian oryx [recently reintroduced], sand gazelle [recently reintroduced], Arabian leopard). Three species (or their rewilding counterpart species) not detected in the survey presently occur in the Nature Reserve as they have been reintroduced (Arabian oryx, sand gazelle, red-necked ostrich) since 2022. Arabian gazelle, Arabian oryx, sand gazelle, red-necked ostrich, and Nubian ibex have been released into rewilding areas in NEOM since 2022. An Arabian gazelle was recorded once by a camera trap, but the individual was likely an animal released from a farm in Sharma Valley. Anecdotal reports of rarer species, such as Arabian gazelle, caracal, and Arabian leopard, are ongoing, particularly from hunters, drivers, hikers, and KSA Border Guards.

Thirty-one species on the target list of 38 species are considered wildlife versus domesticated or feral species. Twenty wildlife species on the list were detected in this survey, while six of seven domestic or feral species were detected.

Some species of wildlife have not yet been confidently recorded (that is, detected through photograph, sighting, or eDNA, DNA, or specimen) recently in NEOM Nature Reserve but may occur in small numbers. These include caracal, Asiatic jackal (recently documented in the adjacent PMBSRR to the south of NEOM), and Indian crested porcupine. Arabian leopard has not been recorded for decades. Some species have been documented in this survey once or a few times, such as striped hyena, Cape hare, sand cat, and monitor lizard, suggesting they occur only in low numbers, are patchily distributed, or are challenging to detect. Some species seem relatively common, including Arabian wolf, Arabian red fox, Blanford's fox, desert hedgehog, wildcat, and Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard.

Relative Abundance & Distribution Patterns

Several wildlife species detected appear to be difficult to detect using unbaited camera traps, possibly due to their rarity, patchy distribution, or low detectability due to their behavior. These are Cape hare, striped hyena, sand cat, desert monitor, Arabian gazelle, caracal, honey badger, and Rüppell's fox, all with only a few detections at a small number of sites. Rüppell's fox was only detected in montane Al Suru plains, Al Sourah lowland sand plains ('granitic sand bowl'), Ras Alshaykh Hamid, and the southern Aqaba foothills. Striped hyena was only detected using camera-traps in the Harrah lava plateaus and wadis and Wadi Ifal alluvial plains. Sand cat was only found in Al Sourah granitic sand plain and a similar habitat near Wadi Aynunah and Wadi Ifal in the lowlands. Rüppell's fox was only detected in the coastal sand and gravel plains and larger montane plains (Al Suru). Cape hares were detected most in Alaqan and the northern border zone, though there are some detections from the harrat, wadis in the Jabal Thaghab area, Wadi Sadr, Al 'Bad Plain, and an observation on the lowland plains adjacent to the western foothills of Jabal az Zuduh. Desert monitor is known from the Mneifa plains and in the Bajdah area of the Hisma Desert, though there are anecdotal reports from other areas of the Hisma Desert and the escarpment near Al Shaq Canyon. Caracal was only possibly detected through identification of scat at a few localities. Unfortunately, no DNA was identified from the scat, which would have been improved confidence in these detections. Indian crested porcupine, Arabian leopard, Asiatic jackal, and domestic horse were species not detected though NEOM is within their original range, they were formerly present, they were recorded nearby or are in domestic settings (horse).

Some wildlife species appear to be common in plains and wadis, including Arabian red fox, domestic dogs, desert hedgehog, and Arabian wolf. Spiny-tailed lizards occur patchily in lowland plains. In foothills and montane areas, several wildlife species are commonly encountered including Blanford's fox, Arabian wildcat, Arabian red fox, rock hyrax, and Nubian ibex. All the high peaks surveyed to date support Nubian ibex, Arabian wildcat, and Blanford's fox. Most higher peaks have rock hyrax and Arabian wolf. Desert hedgehogs are commonly detected in plains and wadis. Sand partridges are common and widespread but appear to prefer rockier habitats rather than 'sand'. Arabian partridge occurs in lower- and mid-elevation montane areas and rocky wadis

only as far north as Jabal ash Shiyati and southward. Chukar partridges were only detected in the Aqaba Ranges, Hisma Desert, Harrat, and at Jabal ad Dibbagh and northwards.

Feral cats were detected at several sites, usually at locations near where humans are often present (for example, sites near livestock camps and the mouth of Wadi Tayyib Ism). Feral or livestock dogs are common and widespread but were not detected in the high mountains. Camels and goats are very common in the plains, wadis, and foothills, though not in the northern border zone with Jordan where camels were detected and observed at only a few sites. Sheep are detected regularly in plains, typically along with goats or, occasionally, in large flocks. Donkey, camel, and goats were three domesticated or feral species that were detected at higher elevations in the mountains. Feral donkey dung has been observed by surveyors very high (over 1,600 m) on Jabal Thaghab coastal range peaks, Jabal az Zuduh, and on Jibal al Lawz. No domestic horses were detected, though they are present on farms.

Overall, goats, camels, sheep, livestock dogs, sand partridge, and Arabian red fox were the most sampled wildlife species. Arabian wildcat, Blanford's fox, and Arabian wolf were regularly detected throughout foothills, wadis, and montane habitats.

Ecological Observations

Wolves were commonly detected at the same locality as livestock, particularly in areas where rocky habitat and wadis were nearby. Some wolves were detected in the high mountains (specifically, Jabal ad Dibbagh and Jibal al Lawz) where no livestock or herders were detected.

Most wildlife species are active in the early evening, night, and early morning. Livestock and people are most active in the day and early evening. However, in localities that have little human activity (for example, Hisma desert habitats near the Jordan border and the eastern entrance to Wadi Tayyib Ism in the Aqaba Range), some wildlife species, such as Nubian ibex, were active in the day and on plains as well as rocky habitat.

The only wild target species seen together on the same image were Arabian red fox and Arabian wolf running together at night at two separate events. The reason for this behavior is unknown, but Arabian red fox may be alerting wolves that they are seen by the fox, foxes may be scavenging for scraps, or foxes may be trying to lure wolves away from dens. Sand, chukar, and Arabian partridge flocks were, in some cases, closely following one another but did not overlap on images in almost all cases. More recent camera trapping on Jabal Shar have detected Arabian partridge and Sand partridge together at the same water pool.

Human Activities

Livestock husbandry and grazing occur throughout NEOM except in the most rugged and highest elevation terrain. Larger herds of camels occur in the Hisma Desert, montane plains of the Madyan

Range, and coastal lowlands. Camels were detected in foothills, wadis, and some higher areas of the Hejaz and Madyan Ranges. Wood and wild plant collecting was detected in wadis in the foothills of the Hejaz and Madyan ranges. Vehicles were regularly observed at sites in the lowland plains, major wadis of the mountain region, and in the Hisma Desert. Most vehicles were associated with livestock herders. Hunters were detected most often in wadis and trails leading to higher peaks, such as Jabal az Zuduh, Jabal ash Shiyati, Jabal ad Dibbagh, Jibal al Lawz, and Jabal Thaghab. Hikers were most common in Wadi Tayyib Ism on the Gulf of Aqaba, Wadi Umm Ararah at Jabal ash Shiyati, and Abu Haraq (Secret) Garden in Bajdah, Hisma Desert. Livestock herders were detected in both seasons but in more localities in the cool season. Hunters were active in both seasons.

Hunter

Species Accounts

DOMESTIC GOAT

Bovidae – *Capra hircus* (Linnaeus 1758)

Figure 5. Domestic goat.

Figure 6. Diel activity for domestic goat.

Remarks

Domestic goats are abundant and widespread livestock. At times a single goat was on its own late in the afternoon but most were associated with flocks. Goats occur in every major ecosystem, grazing in sand and gravel plains, wadis, rocky foothills, and mountains. Goat detections are often accompanied by domestic dogs and livestock herders. Donkeys accompany flocks of sheep and goats on accession. Mixed groups of goats and camels were uncommon, while mixed flocks of sheep and goats were common. Goat flocks detected are typically less than 100 individuals. Goats were not detected in the highest peaks, though they were detected and observed in mountainous areas in rocky wadis and on lower slopes closer to livestock camps. Goats are detected mostly around noon and late afternoon. Some cameras recorded seed pod falls of *Vachellia tortillis* that attracted many birds and small mammals, but which were cleanly vacuumed up as a herd of goats passed through the area.

Figure 7. Camera traps where domestic goat were detected.

Figure 8. Camera traps where domestic goat were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 9. Camera traps where domestic goat were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 10. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for domestic goats. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

NUBIAN IBEX

Bovidae – *Capra nubiana* (Cuvier 1825)

IUCN Conservation Status – Globally Vulnerable (IUCN 2024a, Mallon et al. 2023) – Regional Assessment as Vulnerable C1¹

Figure 11. Nubian ibex.

Figure 12. Diel activity for Nubian ibex.

Remarks

Present on most higher peaks and ranges throughout NEOM. Present on some Hisma sandstone buttes and plateaus. Present in Aqaba Ranges. No detections in harrat. Ibex will forage in plains adjacent to rocky hills in areas where there is little human presence and livestock. This was observed directly and on camera-traps in the Alaqan and KSA-Jordan border areas. Groups up to 15 in size observed, but smaller groups appear to be more common. Nubian ibex require regular visits to waterholes. They scramble and leap over rocks and cliffs with great agility. Nubian ibex are the smallest of the world's ibex. They have curved horns. Males have larger horns with pronounced knobs and dark beards. Ibex have a darkish stripe on their backs. Dominant males occur with groups of females and young. Other males stay in bachelor herds. They have been observed to be active in both the day and night, the latter mostly where there is human disturbance in the day.

¹ Species are classified into one of nine [Red List Categories](#): Extinct, Extinct in the Wild, Critically Endangered, Endangered, Vulnerable, Near Threatened, Least Concern, Data Deficient and Not Evaluated. Vulnerable, Endangered, and Critically Endangered species are considered to be threatened with extinction. Codes following these categories point to the reasons the categories are being assigned to a species and the key and descriptions can be found in IUCN (2012) (Appendix C).

Figure 13. Camera traps and other observations where Nubian ibex was detected.

Figure 14. Camera traps where Nubian ibex was detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 15. Camera traps where Nubian ibex was detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 16. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Nubian ibex. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

ARABIAN GAZELLE

Bovidae – *Gazella arabica* (Liechtenstein 1827)

IUCN Conservation Status – Vulnerable C2a(i)

Figure 19. Arabian gazelle.

Figure 20. Diel activity for Arabian gazelle.

Remarks

Wild Arabian gazelle were observed near the Jordan border (currently within NEOM Nature Reserve) by National Center for Wildlife (NCW) specialists in the late 1980s (OAR Llewellyn, pers. comm. 2025) and along the Gulf of Aqaba coast in 1999 (Al Aqeel & Wachter 1999; Fig. 21). Gazelle specimens collected by NCW in 2000 were tested for species DNA and were found to be *G. arabica*. The Arabian gazelle detected in the present survey was likely released from a farm in Sharma Valley. Arabian gazelles have recently been reintroduced into Mneifa and Bajdah Wildlife Reserves in NEOM. They are distinguished from sand gazelle by more reddish-brown dorsal fur with a blackish band along their flanks and more slender legs and necks. Their faces have darker and more contrasting markings than sand gazelle and their horns are smaller. Underparts are whitish. Arabian gazelle favor rockier habitats with some trees and larger shrubs for browsing. They are able to survive with little to no water. Most active around dusk and dawn. When alarmed they can make prodigious pronging leaps. They are shy and easily disturbed.

Figure 21. Gulf of Aqaba coast localities for gazelle in 2000 (Al Aqeel & Wacher 1999).

Credit: AC Williams

Figure 22. Camera trap where Arabian gazelle was detected.

Figure 23. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Arabian gazelle. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

DORCAS GAZELLE

Bovidae – *Gazella dorcas* (Linnaeus 1758)

IUCN Conservation Status – Regional Vulnerable D1

NO DETECTIONS – POSSIBLY EXTIRPATED

Figure 17. Dorcas gazelle. Credit: MinoZig

Remarks

Dorcas gazelle possibly occurred in the alluvial plains south of Haql and perhaps further south in the coastal lowlands. There is no recent evidence of Dorcas gazelle in NEOM, though they are extant to the north in Jordan and across the Gulf of Aqaba in alluvial plains of the Sinai, Egypt. National Center for Wildlife and Zoological Society of London conducted a reconnaissance for Dorcas gazelle in the alluvial fan habitat south of Haql in 2000 (unpublished report). No evidence of extant Dorcas gazelle was found.

Dorcas Gazelle in NEOM

If Dorcas gazelle once occurred in NEOM they were either *G. dorcas*, *G. (d) saudiya* (afri), or both (if one considers *G. saudiya* as a distinct species from *G. dorcas* [see below for discussion] with the former in inland plains east of the Hejaz and the latter, possibly, in the coastal lowlands around Gulf of Aqaba).

Though there is no direct evidence of either gazelle's occurrence in NEOM ecosystems. However, there is circumstantial evidence that some form of Dorcas gazelle was recently part of NEOM's local fauna. *G. saudiya* once occurred in northwest Saudi Arabia (Harrison & Bates 1991), possibly even within the Hisma Desert and plains of the Tabuk sandstones. They may also have occurred in the plains of the coastal lowlands, but there are no coastal records presently. *G. dorcas*, the 'Saharan' Dorcas gazelle, may have recently been found in the coastal plains along the Gulf of Aqaba south of Haql as an extension of the extant populations of the 'Saharan' Dorcas gazelle that currently occur in adjacent Jordan (Quemsiyeh et al. 1996) and the coastal plains of the Sinai Peninsula (El Alqamy & Baha El Din 2006). The coastal gravel plains south of Haql on the Gulf of Aqaba have similar habitats to those of the nearby coastal plains in Sinai where this gazelle is found. Thus, NEOM may have been a transition or overlap region for *Afri* and the 'Saharan' Dorcas gazelle, irrespective of ones' interpretation of their distinctiveness or relationship, with the details of distribution presently unclear and undocumented.

Taxonomic Considerations

The taxonomy and relatedness of different species of Arabian gazelle have long been discussed and debated. Several species of gazelle have been described from the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, including:

1. *Gazella (dorcas) saudiya*. Afri. The Saudi gazelle ('Dorcass') is now considered to be extinct in the wild (Mallon & Kingswood 2001, Thouless 1991). However, historically, it was common on the gravel and sandy plains in the northwest and southwestern region of the country, especially in the plains to the east of the Hejaz Mountains (Vesey-Fitzgerald 1952, Thouless et al 1991).
2. *Gazella arabica*. Idmi. The Arabian gazelle occurred in the mountains of western Saudi Arabia and northern deserts. It was once common along the coastal plains, ranging up into the highest plains of the interior. Associated with acacia woodlands, it inhabited the rocky habitats of the mountain foothills, rather than the sandy plains.
3. *Gazelle marica*. Reem, or sand gazelle, were once abundant in the open, sandy habitats, especially in the central region of the country.

The putative species *G. saudiya* was considered a sister species to *G. dorcas*, endemic to the Arabian Peninsula by Thouless and colleagues (1991). Since it was first described as a species, *afri* has been synonymized as a subspecies of Dorcas gazelle (*G. dorcas saudiya*) and, subsequently, given species designation (see Hammond et al 2001). Genetic analyses indicate that the genetic distances between *G. dorcas* and the putative species, *G. saudiya* are small, but reciprocally monophyletic, and in the same clade of gazelles of African origin (Hammond et al 2001, Lerp et al 2011, Lerps et al 2013). However, Hammond and colleagues (2021) suggest the putative species *G. saudiya* could be considered a distinct Evolutionary Significant Unit (ESU) of Dorcas for conservation management.

The IUCN Antelope Specialist Group suggested that is unlikely that *Afri* is a separate species and could be treated as a member of the Dorcas clade. Harrison and Bates (1991) suggest that the *Afri* may represent an earlier wave of dispersal into the Arabian Peninsula with a subsequent and much later dispersal event of the 'Saharan' Dorcas gazelle that just reached to the Sinai, Levant, and northwest Arabia.

Genetic testing of known captive populations of purported *G. saudiya* have indicated that the animals are hybridized with other species of gazelle in some captive collections and may not be suitable for reintroduction into the former range of *afri* (Lerp et al 2011, Hammond et al. 2001). Genetic testing indicates that the animals held in the private collection of Sheikh Al Thani, in Al Wabra, Qatar, are likely the most closely related to the museum specimens of *G. saudiya* that were sampled but are *G. dorcas* of African origin (Hammond et al. 2001). The founder populations of Al Wabra were reported to have come from Tareef Afif in Saudi Arabia, which is <150 km away from the location from where the *G. saudiya* museum specimens originated and likely had genetic affiliations to the putative *G. saudiya* in the region (Hammond et al. 2001, Mallon & Kingswood 2001). Thus, we assume that there are no non-hybridized *G. saudiya* in collections.

Figure 18. *Dorcas gazelle.* Credit: P. Sclater 1894

SAND GAZELLE

Bovidae – *Gazella marica* (Thomas 1897)

IUCN Conservation Status – Vulnerable C2a(i)

Figure 24. Sand gazelle. Credit: AC Williams **Figure 25.** Diel activity for sand gazelle.

Remarks

Sand gazelle were likely extirpated from NEOM. Sand gazelle have been reintroduced into Bajdah and Mneifa Wildlife Reserves since 2022. All sand gazelle in NEOM as of 2025 are in fenced, managed reserves. Sand gazelle may have migrated vast distances in seasonal north-south migrations. Little is known of migration patterns in the Tabuk region. Sand gazelle (*Reem*) are smaller, sand-colored antelopes. They have longer black-tipped tails. They appear a bit chunky compared to the Arabian gazelle (*Idmi*). Males are slightly larger with longer and more recurved horns and a pronounced black gland under the eye. It runs fast but does not leap like other gazelles. They can tolerate high temperatures and can survive without free-standing water. Their lungs and livers shrink in dry conditions.

Figure 26. Camera traps where sand gazelle were detected. Mneifa and Bajdah Wildlife Reserves where sand gazelle has been reintroduced are marked by red dots.

Figure 27. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for sand gazelle. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

ARABIAN DORCAS GAZELLE

Bovidae – *Gazella saudiya* (Groves 1988)

IUCN Conservation Status – Extinct

EXTINCT

Figure 28. Saudi Dorcas gazelle, Afri. Credit: de Buffon

Remarks

Saudi Dorcas gazelle, or *Afri*, is extinct. There are no known captive or wild populations. The species was reported to occur in inland foothills and plains east of the Hejaz Range. They are reported to have referred plains and foothills (Morrison & Scott 1939). The species may have been an eastern subspecies of the Dorcas gazelle (see Remarks for Dorcas gazelle).

ARABIAN ORYX (REINTRODUCED)

Bovidae – *Oryx leucoryx* (Pallas 1777)

IUCN Conservation Status – Vulnerable D1

NO DETECTIONS / REINTRODUCED

Figure 29. Arabian oryx. Credit: AC Williams

Remarks

Arabian oryx were Extinct in the Wild, but as of 2024 after captive breeding and reintroductions they are listed as Vulnerable. Arabian oryx have been reintroduced in NEOM at Bajdah Wildlife Reserve, Al Sourah Wildlife Reserve, and Mneifa Wildlife Reserve to date. Arabian oryx once occurred within NEOM based on analysis of their former range (Harrison & Bates 1991) and local petroglyphs depicting Arabian oryx. Arabian oryx are the largest Arabian antelope. Their coat is white with darker legs. The face has dark markings on cheeks, nose, and forehead. The horns are long, slender, and point backwards slightly. Well-adapted to desert conditions with white reflective coat, selective brain cooling, and altering diel activity to avoid hot conditions.

Figure 30. *Arabian oryx petroglyph (center) from Ship Rock, Bajdah, Hisma Desert.*

DOMESTIC SHEEP

Bovidae – *Ovis aries* (Linnaeus 1758)

Figure 31. Domestic sheep.

Figure 32. Diel activity for domestic sheep.

Remarks

Domestic sheep are abundant and widespread. Sheep are often in mixed flocks with goats. At times, large number of sheep are trucked to different areas for grazing. A local breed of sheep with a white head, black eyes, and black body are called *najidi*. Sheep are primarily detected on lowland plains or gravelly hills in the montane region.

Figure 33. Camera traps where domestic sheep were detected.

Figure 34. Camera traps where domestic sheep were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 35. Camera traps where domestic sheep were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 36. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for domestic sheep. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

LESSER KUDU

Bovidae – *Tragelaphus imberbis* (Blythe 1869)

IUCN Conservation Status – Near Threatened (in Africa)

EXTIRPATED – PROPOSED AS A FORMER NATIVE SPECIES

Remarks

- Lesser kudu are proposed as a recent species of the Arabian larger mammal fauna by Harrison and Bates (1991) based on collected skulls.
- Petroglyphs of twisted horn ungulates throughout western Arabia have led some to surmise that these are lesser kudu depictions (Guagnin et al. 2018).
- A twisted horn petroglyph occurs in NEOM just north of Al Suru plain (Golden Calf Altar Heritage Site), though this glyph may actually depict some form of cattle.
- It remains controversial if lesser kudu were a recent native wildlife species in the Arabian Peninsula.
- A related species, greater kudu (*Tragelaphus strepsiceros* Pallas, 1766), may have been extant in the Holocene (Clarke & Alsharif 2025).

Figure 37. Lesser kudu
Credit: Lip Kee Yap

Figure 38. Petroglyph of possible Lesser Kudu in lower left corner, Al Suru, NEOM Nature Reserve

DOMESTIC CAMEL

Camelidae – *Camelus dromedarius* (Linnaeus 1758)

Figure 39. Domestic camel.

Figure 40. Diel activity for domestic camel.

Remarks

Camels are abundant and widespread. Camels are in every ecosystem type, occurring in sand and gravel plains, wadis, rocky foothills, and mountains. Camel detections are often accompanied by livestock herders. Camels are detected throughout the day and early evening. Camel herds are not commonly associated with flocks of goats or sheep or domestic dogs. Tristram's starlings (*Onychognathus tristramii*) were occasionally photographed in association with camels, sometimes riding their backs. This may be an ancient, ongoing interaction since when camels were wild. 'Feral' camels were only observed once on the KSA-Jordan border.

Figure 41. Camera traps where domestic camel were detected.

Figure 42. Camera traps where domestic camel were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 43. Camera traps where domestic camel were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 44. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for domestic camels. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

Petroglyph of possible wild camels from Hisma Desert, NEOM Nature Reserve

ASIATIC (GOLDEN) JACKAL

Canidae – *Canis aureus syriacus* (Linnaeus 1758)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Regional IUCN Status – Near Threatened

Proposed National IUCN Status – Vulnerable (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

NO DETECTIONS OR RECORDS

Figure 45. Asiatic jackal. Credit: PMBSRR camera-trap image from LinkedIn post by PMBSRR.

Remarks

There were no detections or recent records of Asiatic jackal in NEOM. The Asiatic (golden) jackal looks like a small wolf but they are more slender and have longer ears. The fur is brownish/golden to greyish in color and lighter underneath. *Canis aureus* has been recorded from the Azraq Oasis in Jordan (Amr 2012, Eid et al. 2020), Qa' Sharorah wetlands to the west of NEOM (Al Ahmari et al. 2024), and Yemen (Mensor 2023). This species often occurs in association with wetlands and riparian habitats. This species was recently detected in AIUla (Royal Commission of AIUla) using acoustic monitors (Browne et al. In press, Bilancioni et al. 2024) and in the Prince Mohammed bin Salman Royal Reserve (<https://sa.linkedin.com/company/pmbsrr> accessed 2.10.2025) just south of NEOM. *C. a. aureus* is considered the likely subspecies to occur in the NEOM region (Sosale et al. 2023) but *C. a. syriacus* occurs just to the north in Jordan.

DOMESTIC DOG

Canidae – *Canis familiaris* (Linnaeus 1758)

Figure 46. Domestic dog.

Figure 47. Diel activity for domestic dog.

Remarks

One to two domestic dogs commonly accompanied livestock herds. Feral dogs were detected in the coastal lowlands, Ruwafa, and Al Suru plains. However, it is difficult to distinguish a feral dog from a wandering livestock dog. Several wolf-dog hybrids were observed. Both livestock and feral dogs hunt wildlife and can be canid disease vectors to wildlife.

Figure 48. Camera traps where domestic dog were detected.

Figure 49. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for domestic dogs. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

ARABIAN (GREY) WOLF

Canidae – *Canis lupus arabs* (Pocock 1934)

IUCN Conservation Status – Regionally Vulnerable C1

Regional IUCN Status – Near Threatened

Proposed National IUCN Status – Endangered (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

Figure 50. Arabian wolf.

Figure 51. Diel activity for Arabian wolf.

Remarks

Wolves occur in all major ecosystem types and landforms but are most common in the coastal lowlands, Harrat, Hisma Desert, and Madyan Range. A maximum of three wolves in a group were detected, though another survey in NE NEOM photographed 5 wolves together. Typically, only one or two were detected in any given event. Wolves occurred in both areas with livestock and in remote peaks without livestock. Wolves were observed together with Arabian red fox in the same image at two localities. Wolves are detected on camera traps most commonly in the evening and early morning although they are occasionally seen in the day. Wolves can have five young in a litter. They are highly mobile and cover large distances. This subspecies of grey wolf is relatively small in comparison to others. However, some can reach 20 kg and 65 cm at the shoulder. Ears are large. Middle two toes are fused. Tail held more upright when moving and longer legs than any other wild canids in region. Winter fur is thick. They are greyish with yellow and beige tinges in color and lighter underneath. Longer muzzle.

Figure 52. Camera traps where Arabian wolf were detected.

Figure 53. Camera traps where Arabian wolf were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 54. Camera traps where Arabian wolf were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 55. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Arabian wolf. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

Figure 56. Arabian wolf and fox (likely Arabian red fox) in same image.

Figure 57. Arabian wolf and fox (likely Arabian red fox) in same image.

Figure 58. Wolf-dog hybrid, note white forepaw.

BLANFORD'S FOX

Canidae – *Vulpes cana* (Blanford 1877)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Regional IUCN Status – Vulnerable

Proposed National IUCN Status – Vulnerable (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

Figure 59. Blanford's fox.

Figure 60. Diel activity for Blanford's fox.

Remarks

Blanford's fox typically occur in rocky foothills and montane habitats. It is common in the rocky outcrops and foothills of the Madyan Range and Hisma Desert. This small fox has a relatively short and narrow snout and a pronounced bushy, plume-like tail that is darker at the tip. There is a dark band from the upper lip to the eye. Ears are large with prominent white hairs on the front side. Blanford's fox are smaller than Ruppell's fox (*Vulpes rueppellii*) and have bushier tails and smaller ears. They are active both in the day and night. Agile climbers. They den in rocky clefts, not burrows.

Figure 61. Camera traps where Blanford's fox were detected and observations.

Figure 62. Camera traps where Blanford's fox were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 63. Camera traps where Blanford's fox were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 64. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Blanford's fox. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

RÜPPELL'S FOX

Canidae – *Vulpes reuppelli* (Schinz 1825)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Regional IUCN Status – Least Concern

Proposed National IUCN Status – Least Concern (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

Figure 65. Rüppell's fox. Credit: NDS

Figure 66. Diel activity for Rüppell's fox.

Remarks

Rüppell's foxes were detected exclusively in sand plains with rocky outcrops in the lowlands, Al Suru plains, and the Hisma Desert. Rüppell's foxes are rare and may be declining due to competition from the abundant Arabian red fox. In general, this species is distinguished from Arabian red fox by its shorter snout, pronounced black tear marks, relatively full tail with a white tip (red fox have white tail tips). In general, this species is distinguished from Blanford's fox by having a less plumose tail, no black tip on the tail, more reddish coloration at times, and a slightly more pronounced snout. They are desert adapted foxes and do not have to drink much water. This species may be the Arabian Peninsula's ecological counterpart of the Saharan fennec fox.

Figure 67. Camera traps where Rüppell's fox were detected.

Figure 68. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Rüppell's fox. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

ARABIAN RED FOX

Canidae – *Vulpes vulpes arabica* (Thomas 1902)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Regional IUCN Status – Least Concern

Proposed National IUCN Status – Least Concern (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

Figure 69. Arabian red fox.

Figure 70. Diel activity for Arabian red fox.

Remarks

Arabian red fox are the largest and most common fox in NEOM, present in almost all habitats except the highest peaks. Their ears are large with black color on the backs. They are most easily distinguished from other fox species by their long, slender snouts, black ears, and larger size. In the summer, their fur can be short and they may resemble Rüppell's fox somewhat, but their ears are black on the back, there is no pronounced blackish tears on their face, and their snout is much longer. They may or may not have reddish coloration on the fur, which can range from reddish to grayish brown. They have whitish hair on their feet. They survive well in human-modified ecosystems. Arabian red fox numbers may be increasing as top predators decline and human activities provide more food. This increase in fox numbers may create competition with Rüppell's and Blanford's foxes as well as wild felids, with consequential declines in these competitor species as well as prey species. This is the most common carnivore in Saudi Arabia (Al Ahmari et al. 2024). They den in burrows.

Figure 71. Camera traps where Arabian red fox were detected.

Figure 72. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Arabian red fox. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

DOMESTIC DONKEY

Equidae – *Equus africanus asinus* (Linnaeus 1758)

Figure 73. Domestic donkey.
Credit: NEOM Environment

Figure 74. Diel activity for domestic donkey.

Remarks

One to two domestic donkeys are occasionally detected with livestock herders tending flocks of goats and sheep. The donkeys usually are carrying supplies or being ridden. Feral donkey herds have been heard and dung observed on Jabal Marsha. Feral donkeys may compete with Nubian ibex for food and water in montane habitats. A feral donkey herd of 8 individuals was detected on Jabal az Zuduh at over 1,890 m. Nubian ibex were detected in the same habitat. Donkeys were most commonly detected in the afternoon and early evening, though the feral donkeys observed were active at night (~2200 hrs).

Feral donkeys at Jibal al Lawz (Credit: Binish Roobas)

Figure 75. Nature Reserve camera traps where domestic donkey were detected.

Figure 76. Camera traps where domestic donkey were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 77. Camera traps where domestic donkey were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 78. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for domestic donkey. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

Figure 79. Feral donkey on Jabal az Zuduh at 1,890 m.

DOMESTIC HORSE

Equidae – *Equus caballus* (Linnaeus 1758)

NO DETECTIONS

Figure 80. Domestic horse in NEOM.

Remarks

No domestic horses were detected in surveys though some have been observed in NEOM in association with people having them in stables, riding them, and carrying them in trailers. There are no reports of feral horses.

ONAGER

Equidae – *Equus hemionus hemippus* (Saint-Hilaire 1855)

IUCN Conservation Status – Extinct

EXTINCT – NO DETECTIONS / COUNTERPARTS REINTRODUCED TO PMBSRR

Figure 81. Onager. Credit: M Hofmeyr & PMBSRR

Figure 82. Syrian wild ass. Credit: F York 1872

Remarks

Syrian wild ass or onager are extinct since the early 20th Century. In 2024, Prince Mohammed bin Salman Royal Reserve (PMBSRR) reintroduced Persian onager (*Equus hemionus onager*) to Saudi Arabia as an ecological counterpart. NEOM plans to reintroduce onager to NEOM Nature Reserve in the future. Wild ass are more slender than donkeys and have smaller ears, in general. Males have harems. Wild ass live in herds of up to 20 animals. They require free-standing water.

DESERT HEDGEHOG

Erinaceidae – *Paraechinus aethiopicus* (Ehrenberg 1832)

IUCN Conservation Status – Globally LC (Least Concern), Regionally LC

Figure 83. Desert hedgehog.

Figure 84. Diel activity for desert hedgehog.

Remarks

This desert hedgehog is adapted to hyper-arid environments. It is the only species in the region. They are solitary and territorial. They occur in many types of habitats but have not been documented from high mountains yet. They are largely nocturnal and crepuscular. They grow up to 250 mm in length with small tails. They are roundish in appearance and covered in pale brown spines with dark tips. The fur underneath is lighter to whitish in color. Their noses are somewhat pointed and faces have a black mask. Hedgehog ears are elongated. Legs are small and upright.

Figure 85. Camera traps where desert hedgehog were detected.

Figure 86. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for desert hedgehog. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

CHEETAH

Felidae – *Acinoyx jubatus* (Arabian form)

IUCN Conservation Status – EX (Extinct)

EXTIRPATED / ARABIAN FORM EXTINCT

Figure 87 Credit: NL Corkhill (photo taken in southern Iraq, Shamiyah District, from Harrison & Bates 1991)

Remarks

The Arabian cheetah subspecies identify is still being evaluated. DNA from mummified remains in caves—samples varied from 4,000 years to 120,000 years old—from the northern Kingdom suggest the Arabian cheetah may have been a distinct subspecies most closely aligned with the northeast African cheetah rather than *A. j. venaticus* (Asian cheetah). The Kingdom’s National Center for Wildlife is evaluating Arabian cheetah relationships and has developed a National Cheetah Strategy (Al Boug et al. 2024). Cheetah became extinct in the Arabian Peninsula more than 50 years ago. Cheetah once occurred in the NEOM region and were likely one of the top predators of gazelle species. Cheetah are slender cats with round, solid black spots on yellow to brownish yellow background. They have distinctive black tears marks on their face. They once inhabited plains and wadis and mountain ranges. They are active in the day unless there is high human disturbance. They would have maintained large home ranges in NEOM’s arid environment. Males are territorial.

CARACAL

Felidae – *Caracal caracal schmitzi* (Matschie 1912)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern (considered Endangered in Asian portion of their range)

Regional IUCN Status – Least Concern

Proposed National IUCN Status – Near Threatened (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

TWO POSSIBLE SCAT DETECTIONS

Figure 88. NEOM Nature Region, taken at Prince Saud Al-Faisal Center for Wildlife Research, National Center for Wildlife.

Remarks

NEOM biodiversity surveys have had two (possible) caracal scat detections (Clarke & Smithson 2018, Campbell et al. 2024). No caracal were detected by camera-traps. No DNA analysis of the scat was done. NEOM Nature Reserve is within the distribution of caracal. Caracal have been observed in Wadi Rum in Jordan, an extension of the Hisma Desert. Caracal were observed by Saudi Wildlife Authority (now National Center for Wildlife) specialists at Jabal ad Dibbagh and near the Gulf of Aqaba shoreline at Ra's Suwayhil in 1989 (OAR Llewellyn, pers. comm. 2025). A radio-collared male caracal was tracked for 11 months in Harrat al Harrah Protected Area in northern Saudi Arabia and had a range size >1,100 km² and commonly fed on rodents, particularly Libyan Jird (*Meriones libycus*) (Van Heezik & Seddon 1998). Caracal are medium-sized cats with no spots and shorter tails. They have long black tufts of hair sticking up from each ear. They are a light sandy brown color and have a black stripe from nose to the ear. They occur in a range of habitats—rocky foothills, wadis—but are less common in extensive deserts.

Figure 89. Localities where possible caracal scat was detected (red star). Red ovals are areas where caracal were observed by Saudi Wildlife Authority (now NCW) specialists in the late 1980s.

DOMESTIC CAT

Felidae – *Felis catus* (Linnaeus 1758)

Figure 91. Domestic cat.

Figure 92. Diel activity for domestic cat.

Remarks

Feral cats were detected at several sites, all relatively near human activities or settlements. Detections away from towns were usually located near active livestock camps. Feral cats hunt wildlife and may compete for food, water, and shelter with wild felids. Feral cats roam far into natural areas and may introduce diseases into wild cat populations, such as toxoplasma, distemper, feline panleucopaenia virus, leishmaniosis, Feline calici virus, Feline herpes virus, Feline immunodeficiency virus, Feline leukemia virus, and rabies. Feral cats may hybridize with wild cats, though there is currently little information on this available.

Figure 93. Camera traps where domestic cat were detected.

Figure 94. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for domestic cat. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

SAND CAT

Felidae – *Felis margarita* (Loche 1858)

IUCN Conservation Status – Vulnerable

Regional IUCN Status – Near Threatened

Proposed National IUCN Status – Least Concern (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

Figure 95. Sand cat. Credit: NDS

Figure 96. Diel activity for sand cat.

Remarks

Sand cats are small, pale cats with broad heads that inhabit sand plains, usually in association with some rocky outcrops. The larger, triangular ears are a distinguishing feature. The coat is sandy in color with faint black striping and speckling. The face is marked with a dark reddish-fulvous stripe from the edge of each eye backwards, across the cheeks. Sand cats do not retract their claws completely when walking. Males are larger than females. They have dense fur between their toes to protect from heat and cold. They have acute hearing to find prey in habitats with sparse vegetation. They are active at night and in the day. When alarmed they may lay flat and still on the desert surface. Sand cats may dig their own burrows or inhabit old burrows of fox or other animals. Presently, the sand cat subspecies in NEOM is considered to be *Felis margarita thinobia* (previously it was *F. m. harrisoni*). Sand cats have been detected in Ruwafa in the southern Hisma Desert, in the lowland granitic sand plains of Al Sourah, and in sand plains and wadis south of Jabal as Zuduh.

Figure 97. Camera traps where sand cat were detected.

Figure 98. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for sand cat. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

ARABIAN WILD CAT

Felidae – *Felis lybica lybica* (Forster 1780)

IUCN Conservation Status – Near Threatened

Regional IUCN Status – Near Threatened

Proposed National IUCN Status – Least Concern (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

Figure 99. Arabian wild cat.

Figure 100. Diel activity for Arabian wild cat.

Remarks

Wild cats occur in a range of habitats, including sandy and gravelly wadis and plains, rocky outcrops, and mountains. They are usually photographed with camera-traps as single individuals, though two kittens were photographed together in recent surveys. In general, they look like greyish tabby cats, about the same size, with a distinct black stripe on the inside of the front leg. However, there is some variation in pelage pattern and coloration. Camera-trap surveys show no evidence of hybridization from feral/domestic cats. The latter pose a feline disease risk to wild felids. Wild cats are active both in the day and night.

Figure 101. Camera traps where Arabian wild cat were detected.

Figure 102. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Arabian wild cat. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

Lion

Felidae – *Panthera leo* (Linnaeus 1758)

IUCN Conservation Status – Regionally Extinct

EXTIRPATED / REGIONALLY EXTINCT

Figure 103. Asiatic lion. Credit: Priyank Dhani

Remarks

Lions once occurred in the Arabian Peninsula as far south as Yemen (Mensoor 2023). The last records of lions in the Peninsula were from the Twentieth Century (Schnitzler 2011). Ancient petroglyphs of lion occur in NEOM, particularly in the Hisma Desert. These are large wild cats with tawny coats. Males have manes. There is a tuft of black hair at the end of the tail.

NEOM lion petroglyph in Hisma Desert

ARABIAN LEOPARD

Felidae – *Panthera pardus nimr* (Hemprich and Ehrenberg, 1833)

IUCN Conservation Status – Critically Endangered (CR C2a(i))

Regional IUCN Status – Critically Endangered

Proposed National IUCN Status – Critically Endangered (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

NO DETECTIONS

Credit: NEOM Nature Region, taken at Prince Saud Al-Faisal Center for Wildlife Research, National Center for Wildlife

Remarks

Arabian leopard once occurred in NEOM (Gasperetti & Jackson 1990, Aloufi & Amr 2018, Gasperetti & Jackson 1990, Islam 2021). There is no evidence presently that this species still occurs in NEOM. Leopards living in the region's arid environments likely had huge home ranges (Judas et al. 2006). There are regular anecdotal reports of leopards in NEOM from hunters and residents, including at Jabal Imaiq, Jabal Thaghab, Jabal az Zuduh, Jabal ad Dibbagh, Jibal al Lawz, and Jabal Marshah. Arabian leopard scat analyses from southern Arabia have revealed diverse prey, such as gazelle, Nubian ibex, cape hare, rock hyrax, birds, Indian crested porcupine, Ethiopian hedgehog, small rodents, and insects (Al Johany 2007).

Figure 105. Ancient petroglyph of a leopard and ibex from Bajdah in the Hisma Desert.

Figure 106. A mounted Arabian leopard from Jabal Shar, taken in 1952 (photo by Jameel Altaf).

STRIPED HYENA

Hyaenidae – *Hyaena hyaena* (Linnaeus 1758)

IUCN Conservation Status – Vulnerable (C1) Regional Assessment

Regional IUCN Status – Endangered

Proposed National IUCN Status – Endangered (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

Figure 107. Striped hyena.

Credit: NDS

Figure 108. Diel activity for striped hyena.

Remarks

Hyenas occur throughout NEOM, though most often in habitats with rocky habitats. Hyenas have been anecdotally observed visiting rubbish tips in the lowlands. They can break bones for marrow. Their scat often contains whitish bone-derived material. Hyenas are heavily persecuted through hunting, trapping, and poisoning. Hyena body parts are used for traditional remedies. The striped hyena in NEOM is most likely to be *H. h. syriacus* (Pocock 1934) (Harrison & Bates 1991, Al Ahmari et al. 2024). Striped hyenas are distinguished by their relatively large size and sloping-back profile (forelimbs longer than hindlimbs). They have robust forequarters, head, and neck. The body has black vertical stripes and the neck a darkish patch and pronounced mane. They can appear shaggy, particularly in winter. Ears are long and pointed. Solitary or in pairs.

Figure 109. Camera traps where striped hyena were detected.

Figure 110. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for striped hyena. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

INDIAN CRESTED PORCUPINE

Hystricidae – *Hystrix indica* (Kerr 1792)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

NO DETECTIONS OR RECORDS

Figure 111. *Indian Crested Porcupine.*

Credit: Rufus46 Wikipedia

Remarks

Indian crested porcupines are large rodents weighing up to 18 kg. They are covered in modified hairs called quills which offer protection from predation. The longer quills are darker with alternating white and black bands. They have long claws on the forelimbs for burrowing. They burrow and, at times, live in colonies on rocky hillsides. Herbivorous. They are active at night. They can raise and rattle their quills when alarmed. There are no confirmed records of porcupine in NEOM, though there are records in adjacent areas and NEOM is within the species' range.

CAPE HARE

Leporidae – *Lepus capensis arabicus* (Ehrenberg 1833)

IUCN Conservation Status – Near Threatened

Figure 112. Cape hare.

Figure 113. Diel activity for Cape hare.

Remarks

Cape hare are diminished through hunting and habitat degradation. Observations are primarily at night and the early morning. They are most abundant in NEOM on the Hisma Desert border region with Jordan. Single individuals of hare are usually photographed by camera-traps, though there are a few detections have two hares together. These are smaller hares with long, black-tipped ears. The eyes have a white ring and head is angular. They are sand-colored with white underparts and a fluffy tail black on top and white underneath. The hind limbs are a pale rufous. Largely nocturnal and solitary. They can survive without free-standing water. Burrows.

Figure 114. Camera traps where Cape hares were detected.

Figure 115. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Cape hare. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

RATEL or HONEY BADGER

Mustelidae – *Mellivora capensis pumilio* (Schreber 1776)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Regional IUCN Status – Near Threatened (near VU C1)

Proposed National IUCN Status – Near Threatened (Al Ahmari et al. 2024)

Figure 116. Honey badger.

Credit: NDS

Figure 117. Diel activity for honey badger.

Remarks

Honey badgers are highly active, voracious omnivores. They are medium-sized close to the size of a larger fox. They have a compact, robust body with a black underside and face and a broad band of white fur on top that runs from just above the eyes to the tip of the tail. Short ears and strong forelimbs with large claws. Honey badgers are scarce in NEOM, being recorded recently only from the Hisma Desert and harrat lava plateaus, though they occur in most habitats except extensive dunefields. They are nomadic and cover great distances. They are active in the day in areas with less disturbance and are also active at night. They are heavily persecuted through hunting, trapping, and poisoning. They are omnivorous, though they may be capable of preying on larger animals, such as smaller ungulates.

Figure 118. Camera traps where honey badgers were detected.

Figure 119. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for honey badger. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

ROCK HYRAX

Procaviidae – *Procavia capensis* (Pallas 1766)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Figure 120. Rock hyrax.

Figure 121. Diel activity for rock hyrax.

Remarks

Hyrax live in rocky outcrops and mountains. They live in rocky habitats of the lowlands and mountains, as well as the Hisma Desert. They are social animals living in groups. They are chunky, rodent-like mammals with solid builds and smaller legs. They run across and between rocks and cliffs with great agility. Hyrax have short, rounded ears, short snouts, large round eyes, and no tail. They may whistle when alarmed. They are widely hunted for food and parts for remedies.

Figure 122. Camera traps where rock hyrax were detected.

Figure 123. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for rock hyrax. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

EGYPTIAN SPINY-TAILED LIZARD

Agamidae – *Uromastyx aegyptica* (Forskål 1775)

IUCN Conservation Status – Vulnerable

Figure 124. Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard.

Figure 125. Diel activity for Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard.

Remarks

Egyptian spiny-tail lizards (STL) are active during the hottest part of the day in the warm season, in general. They show little activity during the cooler months. STL typically occur on compacted sand and gravel plains. At times, burrows are clustered. Camera-trap surveys are not efficient for surveys of distribution or populations of STL. Targeted surveys in the coastal lowland plains and Hisma Desert show them to be more abundant and widely distributed than the camera-trap surveys suggest.

Figure 126. Camera traps where Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard were detected.

Figure 127. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

DESERT MONITOR

Varanidae – *Varanus griseus* (Daudin 1803)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Figure 128. Desert monitor

Figure 129. Diel activity for desert monitor.

Remarks

Desert monitors are voracious predators. They are adept at climbing trees and rocks and going into crevices in search of food. They were detected at a few sites in the Hisma Desert and coastal lowlands. Ferguson and Rowntree (2024) recorded desert monitors ten times during reptile surveys since 2021, four times at Midyan (including on a trail camera), three times in northwest NEOM, twice at Aqaba Mountain, and once at Ras Alsheikh Hamid. They appear to behave quite secretly within the region and are difficult to observe, quickly escaping into burrows when approached.

Figure 130. Camera traps where desert monitors were detected.

Figure 131. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for desert monitor. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

HOUBARA BUSTARD

Otididae – *Chlamydotis undulata macqueenii* (Jaquin 1784)

IUCN Conservation Status – Vulnerable

NO DETECTIONS

Figure 132. Houbara bustard. Credit: Shankar S

Remarks

Houbara bustard have been reduced throughout the Kingdom. The greatest threats to the houbara bustard have been habitat destruction by overgrazing (camels, goats and sheep), and hunting. Mortality from striking transmission lines is high (Schoobrak 2023). Resident populations require large spaces (1,000 km² – 2,000 km²) with suitable habitat (grassland, shrubs, bushes) that remain below 30 degrees during the breeding period (Dec-March). If temperatures rise above 30 degrees, the bustards will not breed. However, they will use areas below this temperature for feeding. Commonly one will find between 2-4 individuals per square kilometer in areas of suitable habitat, which may form a combination of resident and migratory birds. The Prince Mohammed bin Salman Houbara Conservation Foundation is working to restore Houbara populations throughout the Kingdom.

ARABIAN PARTRIDGE

Phasianidae – *Alectoris melanocephala* (Rüppell 1835)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Figure 133. Arabian partridge.

Figure 134. Diel activity for Arabian partridge.

Remarks

The Arabian partridge was detected in mountainous areas as far north as Jabal az Zuduh and Jabal ash Shiyati in NEOM. The Arabian partridge was sympatric with chukar partridge starting at Jabal ash Shiyati southward in mountains and rocky foothills. Arabian partridge was not detected in the harrat whereas chukar partridge and sand partridge were. Arabian partridge was not detected in the Aqaba Range. Sand partridges were commonly detected at Arabian partridge sites. Arabian partridge favored rocky wadis in the foothills of larger mountains. They may go higher in the mountains but were not detected. Group sizes were similar to chukar partridge group size (roughly 5 to 10 individuals) but generally less than those of sand partridge which commonly had flocks of 10 to 20 individuals.

Figure 135. Camera traps where Arabian partridge were detected.

Figure 136 Camera traps where Arabian partridge were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 137. Camera traps where Arabian partridge were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 138. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for Arabian partridge. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

CHUKAR PARTRIDGE

Phasianidae – *Alectoris chukar* (Gray 1830)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Figure 139. Chukar partridge.

Figure 140. Diel activity for chukar partridge.

Remarks

Chukar partridge was detected in mountainous areas as far south as Jabal ad Dibbagh and westward into the Aqaba Ranges. They were also detected in the Hisma Desert and harrat. Sand partridges were commonly detected at chukar partridge sites. Chukar partridge favored rocky wadis and rocky habitat in the foothills and heights of larger mountains. Group sizes were similar to Arabian partridge group size (5 to 10 individuals) but, generally, less than those of sand partridge (commonly 10 to 20 individuals).

Figure 141. Camera traps where chukar partridge were detected.

Figure 142. Camera traps where chukar partridge were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 143. Camera traps where chukar partridge were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 144. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for chukar partridge. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

SAND PARTRIDGE

Phasianidae – *Ammoperdix heyi* (Temminck 1825)

IUCN Conservation Status – Least Concern

Figure 145. Sand partridge.

Figure 146. Diel activity for sand partridge.

Remarks

Sand partridges were commonly detected in rocky areas throughout NEOM. They favor rocky habitat rather than sand, despite their name, though they were detected on Hisma Desert sands. They are the most widespread and abundant of the partridges, often occurring in larger flocks up to 20 or more birds. They have been observed in association with both Chukar and Arabian partridges, that is, closely following other species' flocks after they have walked through an area. Arabian and sand partridges were photographed together at a water pool on Jabal Shar in one event.

Figure 147. Camera traps where sand partridge were detected.

Figure 148. Camera traps where sand partridge were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 149. Camera traps where sand partridge were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 150. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for sand partridge. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

RED-NECKED OSTRICH

Struthionidae – *Struthio camelus camelus* (Linnaeus 1758)

IUCN Conservation Status – Critically Endangered

NO DETECTIONS / REINTRODUCED COUNTERPART SPECIES OF EXTINCT FORM

Figure 151. Red-necked ostrich. Credit: AC Williams

Remarks

The Arabian or Syrian ostrich subspecies, *Struthio camelus syriacus*, is extinct. The red-necked ostrich from North Africa has been introduced as an ecological counterpart subspecies. Both *S. c. syriacus* and *S. c. camelus* are considered the same subspecies by some ornithologists. Old ostrich eggshell fragments have been found in Mneifa, Al Sourah, and Bajdah showing the species once could be found in lowland and plateau habitats. No ostrich were detected as there were no cameras in ostrich release areas during the survey. Reintroduced counterpart ostrich presently occurs only in Mneifa Wildlife Reserve, Al Sourah Wildlife Reserve, and Bajdah Wildlife Reserve as of 2024.

Ostrich and Arabian oryx petroglyph from Hisma Desert

Human Activity

LIVESTOCK HERDERS

Figure 152. Livestock herder.

Figure 153. Diel activity for livestock herders.

Remarks

Livestock was typically associated with livestock herders. The domestic species associated with herders include goats, sheep, camels, donkeys, and domestic dogs. Herders were detected walking, riding donkeys, riding in vehicles, and riding camels. Vehicles with people often accompanied livestock.

Figure 154. Camera traps where livestock herders were detected.

Figure 155. Camera traps where livestock herders were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 156. Camera traps where livestock herders were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 157. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for livestock herders. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

HUNTERS

Figure 158. Hunter.

Figure 159. Diel activity for hunters.

Remarks

Hunting remains widespread and intensive as of 2024. During the bird migration season many different species of bird are hunted in the lowlands and the coastal areas. Various species of dove are trapped as bait for falconry. Opportunistic hunting is common when wildlife is encountered. Nubian ibex are hunted in the mountains by local people and hunters from the broader region, even on the highest peaks. Hunters in the mountains often hunt at night and spend several days in the mountains. Hunters were observed heading into the mountains and returning after 1 to 3 days by the camera-traps. Hunters were identified based on the presence of rifles, camouflage, and binoculars. Hunters were detected in all major mountain areas except in border areas with Jordan.

Figure 160. Camera traps where hunters were detected.

Figure 161. Camera traps where hunters were detected in the hot season (June 1 to September 30).

Figure 162. Camera traps where hunters were detected in the cool season (October 1 to May 31).

Figure 163. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for hunters. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

PLANT/WOOD COLLECTORS

Figure 164. Plant/wood collector.

Figure 165. Diel activity for plant/wood collectors.

Remarks

Local people will often collect firewood, plant material, and food and medicinal plants from the wild. Livestock herders will often collect wood and food and medicinal plants while tending to livestock. No commercial wood cutters and charcoal producers were detected, though this practice continues throughout NEOM.

Figure 166. Camera traps where plant/wood collectors were detected.

Figure 167. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for plant/wood collectors. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

HIKERS

Figure 168. Hikers.

Figure 169. Diel activity for hikers.

Remarks

People not actively engaged in plant collecting, livestock herding, or hunting were categorized as ‘hikers’. While one cannot determine their reason for being at a site, the reasons may range from, as examples, walking between settlements and looking for lost livestock to carrying out surveys or tourism. People associated with camera-trap deployment and retrieval were not counted. Hikers are detected most in the late afternoon and early evening. People sometimes did not see the camera-traps. Sometimes they saw them and at times they smiled and waved and made other gestures. They built fires, they sat under trees, they moved cameras to face the sky or the ground. Some cameras were damaged and SD cards taken. Some cameras were crushed, burned, or stolen.

Figure 170. Camera traps where hikers were detected.

Figure 171. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for hikers. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

DRIVING – VEHICLES

Figure 172. Vehicles.

Figure 173. Vehicle activity.

Remarks

Vehicle tracks are common throughout undeveloped and natural habitats of NEOM Nature Reserve. Offroad vehicle driving is common, even up steep sand dunes. Drivers may be associated with livestock camps, homesteads, tourists, picnickers, surveyors, hunters, or engaged in a range of activities. Most of the vehicles detected were associated with livestock herding. Most vehicles were detected in the late afternoon. No motorcycles and only one larger water truck was detected.

Figure 174. Nature Reserve camera traps where vehicles were detected.

Figure 175. Relative detection rates at different camera traps for vehicles. Only Nature Reserve camera-traps were used to assess detection rates. Blue dots are camera-traps at which there was no detection. Grids with no black or blue dots were not sampled.

DISCUSSION

Representative Large Terrestrial Vertebrate Assemblages

Most species observed occur widely throughout NEOM Nature Reserve and many occur in a wide range of habitat types. However, larger sand and gravel plains currently tend to be inhabited by Arabian red fox, sand cat, desert hedgehog, Cape hare, desert monitor, Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard, and Rüppell's foxes. In the past, sand gazelle, Arabian oryx, cheetah, ostrich, and Dorcas gazelle may have occurred in these habitats. Arabian wolf and Nubian ibex occur in these habitats, at times, but ibex favor areas adjacent to rocky outcrops and montane foothills. Rocky outcrops, rocky foothills, and mountains support Nubian ibex, rocky hyrax, Arabian wolf, Arabian wild cat, chukar partridge, sand partridge, and Blanford's fox. Rocky, sand, and gravel wadis in foothills often have Arabian red fox, rock hyrax, Arabian wolf, Cape hare, Arabian wild cat, chukar, Arabian and sand partridge, desert hedgehog, Blanford's fox, and, at times, Nubian ibex. Hyena and caracal may possibly occur here. Arabian gazelle might occur here. The *harrat*, in this survey, supports wildlife such as striped hyena, honey badger, Arabian red fox, chukar partridge, Arabian wolf, and desert hedgehog. The Hisma Desert supports desert monitor, Nubian ibex, rock hyrax, Arabian red fox, sand partridge, Blanford's fox, Rüppell's fox, sand cat, Arabian wolf, chukar partridge, honey badger, and desert hedgehog. In the past, sand gazelle, Arabian oryx, Syrian ostrich, cheetah, onager, lion, *Afri*, and Arabian gazelle are likely to have occurred in the Hisma Desert plains and wadis.

Wildlife 'Hotspots'

Several present-day 'hotspots' of wildlife abundance and richness are highlighted by this survey. These typically are areas that are more remote or protected from intensive human activities (Fig. 176). These include the Jibal al Lawz range, the Jabal Marsha and Jabal Thaghab ranges and coastal montane watersheds along the central-east Gulf of Aqaba coast (including Wadi Tayyib Ism), the central KSA border zone with Jordan and Jabal Imaiq and ranges and wadis associated with this complex area, Jabal ash Shiyati massif, Jibal ad Dibbagh massif, Jabal az Zuduh massif, Jabal Shar, and the *harrat* plateaus and associated wadis. The steepest portions all along the main escarpment require further surveys to assess wildlife occurrence and use in this potentially critical corridor habitat for ibex, wolves, and other species. The Wadi Damm wadis and plateaus require further wildlife surveys as well to assess their importance as wildlife refugia. Both, Arabian wolf and Nubian ibex occur in this area. Overall, the most 'intact' wildlife communities surveyed in this effort were the plains and mountains along the central border area with Jordan and the high elevations of Jibal ad Dibbagh. Both areas have low levels of hunting only and there is little to no livestock grazing presently.

Al Sourah Plains and the Wadi Ifal and Wadi Khurays sand plain habitats in the coastal lowlands are the last large, undeveloped 'granitic sand bowl' habitats that support sand cat and Rüppell's

fox. The sand plains adjacent to the SW faces of Jibal ad Dibbagh and Jabal Shar offer similar, but smaller, habitats that are both presently heavily degraded by intensive livestock grazing (Fig. 176).

Figure 176. Major biophysical features and place names in NEOM.

Long-Term Change in the Larger Terrestrial Vertebrate Fauna of NEOM Nature Reserve
Reduction in the richness and changes to the nature (for example, complexity of food webs, guild structure, biomass profiles, resilience to disturbance) of the larger terrestrial vertebrate fauna have occurred in the NEOM Nature Reserve over the past few millennia. These changes can be characterized in three general phases:

The first phase corresponds roughly 2,000 years ago and before when (i) wild cattle (auroch [*Bos primigenius*]) disappeared due to, in part, the climate becoming drier resulting in less forage and water and (ii) wild camel were lost as the species was fully domesticated (see Guagnin et al. 2018, Clarke & Al Sharif 2025). The second phase was the loss of several larger species due to the cumulative impacts of (i) habitat loss and degradation of forage and water sources through increased pastoralism and overexploitation by domestic goats, sheep, donkeys, and camels, (ii) damage to desert vegetation and water through increased off-road driving, (iii) overhunting exacerbated through the advent of high-powered rifles and fast vehicles, (iv) poisoning of predators and secondary poisoning of larger scavengers, and (v) a presumed greater prevalence of diseases jumping from domestic livestock, cats, and dogs. Species lost in this second phase include the Asiatic lion (*Panthera leo*, extirpated with Arabian form extinct, lost in NEOM area 100+ years ago), onager (*Equus hemionus hemippus* [Extinct subspecies] onager extirpated, lost in NEOM area 50+ years ago, ecological counterpart *Equus hemionus* extant subspecies), Arabian cheetah (*Acinonyx jubatus* Arabian subspecies Extinct, lost in NEOM area 50+ years ago), Arabian/Syrian ostrich (*Struthio camelus syriacus* Extinct, lost in NEOM area 50+ years ago, red-necked ostrich [*Struthio camelus camelus*] is an ecological counterpart to the native subspecies to be rewilded), Arabian oryx (*Oryx leucoryx* was Extinct in the Wild, reintroduced, lost in NEOM area 50+ years ago), Arabian leopard (*Panthera pardus nimr*, likely extirpated, likely lost in the last few decades, historical records), Saudi Dorcas gazelle (*Gazella d. saudiya* [*G. saudiya*], *Afri*, Extinct, lost in NEOM area 50+ years ago), and sand gazelle (*Gazella marica*, extirpated, lost in NEOM area 50+ years ago). The species lost in this phase are characterized as larger predators and herbivores often targeted by hunters.

The third phase, occurring now, represents an additional wave of loss through an ongoing decline in more resilient predators, omnivores, and herbivores, such as Cape hare, rock hyrax (*Procavia capensis*), Nubian ibex (*Capra nubiana*), striped hyena (*Hyaena hyaena*), caracal (*Caracal caracal*), Rüppels fox (*Vulpes ruepellii*), ratel or honey badger (*Mellivora capensis*), spiny-tailed lizard, vultures (cinereous vulture *Aepygius monachus*, Egyptian vulture *Neophron percnopterus*, griffon vulture *Gyps fulvus*), lammergeier (*Gypaetus barbatus*), Houbara bustard (*Chlamydotis undulata*), and sand cat (*Felis margarita*). The drivers of change are similar for the second and third phase, but habitat and water source degradation is advanced, more poisons are used to kill predators (and, consequently, scavengers), antibiotics used on livestock are toxic to vultures, and the intensity of overgrazing and hunting is much increased and widespread. Some larger wildlife species in the NEOM Nature Reserve appear to be relatively common at present. These include Arabian red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), Arabian wolf (*Canis lupus*), Blanford's fox (*Vulpes cana*), wildcat (*Felis lybica*), and desert hedgehog (*Paraechinus aethiopicus*).

The loss of larger vertebrates, larger predators, and larger scavengers in NEOM's faunal assemblages has cascading consequences in the ecosystem. For example, smaller-sized predators,

such as foxes, may become more abundant as they are released from predation by larger predators, such as leopard and ratel ('mesopredator release' [Crooks & Soulé 1999, Haswell et al. 2017, but see Ritchie & Johnson 2009, Castle et al. 2021]). More foxes may result in greater predation on small mammals, reptiles, and birds whose populations, subsequently, become less abundant and have diminished ecological roles. The predation of wolves, today, may keep some mesopredator populations in check (see Faure et al. 2024). The fear of larger predators in riparian vegetation in wadis may inhibit wildlife and livestock from entering vegetated areas resulting in denser riparian vegetation (Ripple & Beschta 2004 but see Marris 2014). With the loss of larger predators, riparian habitats may become increasingly degraded from heavy browsing, grazing, and trampling by herbivorous wildlife (livestock are relatively protected by herders and livestock dogs). The loss of wild ungulate populations has also decreased available carrion for vultures and other scavengers.

Assessing Intactness of the Larger Terrestrial Vertebrate Fauna of NEOM Nature Reserve

In ecosystems around the world, one can generally categorize the 'intactness' of larger terrestrial vertebrate assemblages (that is, terrestrial megafauna) along a continuum of intactness (that is, presence of naturally occurring species and ecological guilds in populations within their natural range of variation and maintaining their functional role in an ecosystem) as follows (Fig. 177):

- (1) *intact* (that is, the full complement of naturally occurring species and guilds present within their natural ranges of variation and maintaining their ecological roles);
- (2) *relatively intact* (that is, most, but not all, of naturally occurring species and guilds present within their natural ranges of variation and maintaining their ecological roles);
- (3) *diminished* (that is, most to all species are present but in reduced abundance below their estimated natural range of variation and some ecological roles and guilds becoming compromised, many to all higher-level predators are lost and larger-bodied species lost);
- (4) *depleted* (that is, more vulnerable species are missing along with their ecological roles and whole functional guilds are largely gone); and
- (5) *largely extirpated* in an 'empty forest' or 'empty desert' syndrome (Redford 1992, Harrison 2011, Wilkie et al. 2011, Durant et al. 2014, Brito et al. 2018) condition (that is, all but the least vulnerable larger vertebrates have been extirpated along with their ecological roles) (Fig. 177).

Given that the 2024 NEOM Nature Reserve fauna has (1) lost most of its top and larger predators (for example, cheetah, lion, Arabian leopard) and larger herbivores (for example, Arabian oryx, gazelles), (2) larger scavengers like vultures are uncommon to rare, (3) mesopredators such as Arabian red fox are widespread and abundant, and (4) the much of the faunal biomass is accounted for by domestic and feral livestock and the wildlife biomass is largely represented by smaller

predators, omnivores, and herbivores, then we consider the current larger terrestrial vertebrate fauna is most accurately categorized as being in a transition from a diminished to a depleted state, particularly if trends of loss continue (refer to Fig. 177).

Notably, missing from the current wildlife assemblage are most top predators (Arabian wolf are an exception) and larger herbivores (Nubian ibex are an exception), a pattern consistent with defaunation processes in natural ecosystems around the world, including xeric regions (see Durant et al. 2014, Brito et al. 2018, Canassa et al. 2025). NEOM Nature Reserve does retain relatively abundant populations of Arabian wolf and Nubian ibex, as well as Blanford's fox and Arabian wild cat. It still maintains a rich and diverse assemblage of mesopredators, including wolf, red fox, Blanford's fox, Rüppell's fox (rare), sand cat (rare), Arabian wild cat, monitor lizards, and honey badger (rare). Vultures are greatly diminished. In short, NEOM Nature Reserve is remarkable for the wildlife that it still retains, but there is much restoration required to shift the intactness of the fauna from a depleted state to a relatively intact state.

If hunting and poisoning was controlled, abundant prey became available, and disturbance limited in core and dispersal areas within larger natural landscapes, then populations of both leopard and cheetah have good potential to be restored to NEOM Nature Reserve. Leopards are documented to have occurred in the Madyan Range within NEOM. Indeed, the potential is high for restoration of the larger vertebrate fauna as there currently is only minor development of natural landscapes, there are widespread and viable source populations of many species, connectivity throughout natural landscapes can still be maintained, restored, and managed, and there exists strong support to restore native Arabian ecosystems in NEOM Nature Reserve and throughout the Kingdom. Rewilding and greening initiatives are already underway and have shown great promise in targeted landscapes. However, faunal restoration efforts must be supported by reduction and cessation of key threats to wildlife and ecosystems, including intensive livestock grazing, habitat degradation from offroad driving, wood cutting, hunting, and loss and degradation of key water sources.

Figure 177. A conceptual model of defaunation status categories of the megafauna of the xeric ecosystems of the NEOM Nature Reserve, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Several extinct and extirpated species are shown, including lion, cheetah, Arabian leopard, onager, Arabian oryx, sand gazelle, and Syrian ostrich. Wild camels were members of the ecosystem several thousand years ago (wild camels not shown). Golden jackal is not shown. The Nature Reserve has lowland coastal granitic and gypseous sand deserts, high granitic mountains, sandstone plateaus and dunes, and lava plateaus as major habitats. The intact and relatively intact states likely were present within the last 100 years (Harrison & Bates 1991). As defaunation proceeds, certain species and guilds are reduced or extirpated over time. Some species may become more prevalent. Livestock and feral domestic species are shown outside of the continuum. Typically, livestock will be more abundant and widespread towards the 'depleted' and 'empty desert' states (livestock species silhouettes shown at the bottom left corner outside of the triangle). We estimate that the larger terrestrial fauna in NEOM Nature Reserve is currently (2024) at the transition from a diminished to depleted state.

Abundance

The survey approach used here does not lend itself to direct counts or relative estimates of abundance of different wildlife and livestock species. Detection rates may correlate more with activity than with abundance. However, some general patterns do appear from the data. For example, Arabian red foxes are abundant and widespread, which may be a result, in part, of the species' ability to adapt and survive in habitats with high human activity. Considering Arabian red fox as 'super abundant', that is, occurring at densities beyond their estimated natural range of variation may be appropriate, but there is no prior data for comparison. However, their current abundance certainly makes them important competitors with other mesopredators and predators on prey species. Some species, like desert hedgehog, Arabian wild cat, Blanford's fox, and partridges may have populations close to their natural range of variation as they face minor anthropogenic threats and habitats remain favorable. Sand cat, Rüppell's fox, striped hyena, desert monitor, caracal (possible), and honey badger appear to be quite rare or poorly sampled through this survey approach. Of course, Arabian oryx, sand gazelle, and ostrich were not present prior to rewilding efforts. Arabian gazelle and Dorcas gazelle may be present in the wild, but they were not detected and are clearly very rare if they do persist.

Distribution of Wildlife

As expected, lowland habitats, foothill wadis, and montane plains are dominated by domestic livestock in sampled faunal assemblages. Wildlife species occur here too, but more commonly dominate detection events in samples from montane foothills, higher elevation rocky terrain, and low human-disturbance areas, such as the security zones near the Jordan Border and the highest peaks. Some wildlife species are predictable in their distribution, such as sand cat, Rüppell's foxes, and Egyptian spiny-tailed lizards being found only in sandy and gravelly plain habitats and Blanford's fox and Arabian partridges being found only in rockier habitats. Chukar and sand partridges also occur in harrat lava plains and sandy plain/rocky outcrop habitats of the Hisma Desert. Nubian ibex occur only in mountainous areas of the Madyan and Aqaba Ranges and the sandstone buttes and plateaus of the Hisma Desert.

Guilds & Biomass

Larger Predators – This survey confirms that higher-level predators are few in species and numbers in the NEOM Nature Reserve. Only wolves and domestic dogs function as larger predators currently. Honey badger, hyena, and caracal (if present) are exceedingly rare. More intact xeric faunal assemblages and ecosystems would have an increased richness and larger population sizes of native higher-level predators, such as Arabian leopard, cheetah (in the past), caracal, Arabian wolf, striped hyena, and honey badger.

Mesopredators – Arabian red foxes are abundant and widespread due, perhaps, to their ability to survive in areas where people are active, their broad tolerances for diverse habitats, scarcity of larger predators that prey on foxes, and the species' aggressiveness with other competing species, such as Rüppell's fox, Blanford's fox (Faure et al. 2024), Arabian wild cat, and sand cat. Red fox are uncommon on the highest mountains. However, the harsh sand plains of the coastal lowlands, granitic sand bowls, and Hisma desert offer favorable habitat for sand cat and Rüppell's fox and the rocky outcrops, foothills, and mountains support Arabian wild cat and Blanford's fox. These two challenging habitats may act, in some ways, as competitive refugia, and allow these competitors of Arabian red fox to persist in the landscape. The current mesopredator community of NEOM Nature Reserve remains remarkably diverse with Arabian red fox, Rüppell's fox, Blanford's fox, Arabian wild cat, sand cat, caracal, desert monitor, and honey badger.

Larger Herbivores – Wild species of larger herbivores in NEOM Nature Reserve are currently limited to Nubian ibex (except within rewilding areas with reintroduced oryx, gazelle, and ostrich). The role of large herbivores has been largely taken over by domesticated camels, goats, sheep, and donkey. Animal biomass of larger herbivores primarily resides in domestic livestock currently.

Larger Scavengers – Vultures and striped hyena are exceedingly rare. Dogs, ravens, foxes, and wolves are common scavengers presently.

Diel Activity

Presently, most wildlife species are primarily detected at night in NEOM Nature Reserve, except for largely diurnal species, such as partridges, Egyptian spiny-tailed lizard, and desert monitor. This is likely to avoid disturbance from human activities. Camera-trap locations on the KSA border with Jordan where livestock grazing and other human activities are restricted and very low showed that Nubian ibex, Arabian wolf, Arabian wild cat, and foxes were more active in the day than in areas away from the border. Similarly, camera-traps at some of the highest, most remote peaks, such as Jibal ad Dibbagh and Jabal az Zuduh, commonly captured images of wolf and ibex active in the day. Humans are most active in the late afternoon and early evening, in general, though livestock herders remain with their flocks all day.

Seasonality

Some species were detected at more cameras in the lowlands during the cool season. These include, among the species evaluated, the following species: Nubian ibex, sand partridge, chukar partridge, Arabian wolf, and Blanford's fox. Some species may be more active in the cooler season, thus leading to more detections. More mobile species, such as Arabian wolf and Nubian ibex, may shift to higher elevations in the hot season to find cooler temperatures, water, and food. This requires further evaluation, but the detection data could support seasonal movements along elevational gradients for some species.

Corridors & Crossings

As one might expect, camera-traps located in wadis captured more images of wildlife than those placed in rocky terrain. In some cases, wolf and ibex were photographed moving downwards in wadis in the early evening and upwards to higher elevations in the early morning. NEOM Nature Reserve will be monitoring wildlife use in proposed and managed wildlife corridors and highway crossings (Wikramanayake et al. in review).

Threats & Pressures

This survey confirmed that livestock grazing is presently intensive and widespread in NEOM Nature Reserve (Gallacher & Marino 2021, Brown & Ayasrah 2023, Parr & Mukhtar 2023). The grazing pressure can be very high in places. For example, two camera-trap localities, one in Al Sourah plains and one in a broad wadi in the Harrat, experienced livestock grazing an average 4.8 and 12.1 days a month, respectively. Camels, goats, and sheep are commonly observed almost everywhere except in the highest mountains. Overgrazing causes loss and simplification of vegetation and impedes regeneration of trees and shrubs. Overgrazing of livestock degrades land surfaces, riparian habitats, and water sources. Overgrazing of livestock has a strong and long-term negative impact on wildlife habitat and wildlife populations. Camels were common in lowland plains, montane plains, Hisma plains, and *harrat*. Camels were commonly photographed in larger herds without goats or sheep present, with some exceptions. Goats were often accompanied by sheep, livestock dogs, donkeys, and livestock herders, and, at times, with vehicles.

Feral donkeys were detected on some of the highest peaks, potentially competing with Nubian ibex for forage and water. Livestock can transmit diseases to wildlife, as well. Domestic cats and dogs kill wildlife, wolf-dog hybrids have been documented (including in this survey), and diseases can be transmitted to wild congeners (for example, Amin et al. 2021).

Hunting was detected in this survey primarily at camera traps placed at wadis that lead into the highlands where ibex hunting occurs and on the high peaks. Hunters were observed in most mountainous areas surveyed. Seasonal bird hunting in the coastal lowlands remains intense and widespread, but our sampling methods do not pick up this form of hunting. Hunting has a major impact on vulnerable wildlife populations.

Off road driving damages natural land surfaces, degrades wadis, and harms soil and dune-dwelling species. Vehicle tracks can destroy and damage plants and retard regeneration, as well as killing smaller animals outright. Many off road vehicles were detected through the camera-trap surveys.

Woodcutting was not detected through the cameras, but it has been documented in many areas throughout NEOM. Some of the woodcutting is for local use, but some appears to be for commercial selling of firewood and charcoal. Given the important keystone function of trees in

xeric ecosystems, that NEOM has few trees, and the bigger ones are likely quite old, extensive woodcutting can have major and long-lasting impacts on the ecosystem.

Rewilding in NEOM Nature Reserve

Rewilding is defined as “*the process of rebuilding, following major human disturbance, a natural ecosystem by restoring natural processes and the complete or near complete food-web at all trophic levels as a self-sustaining and resilient ecosystem using biota that would have been present had the disturbance not occurred*” (IUCN 2024b). The NEOM Rewilding Strategy emphasizes trophic rewilding that uses species introductions to restore top-down trophic interactions and associated trophic cascades to promote self-regulating biodiverse ecosystems (Svenning et al. 2016). Restoring the ecological role of top predators, for example, can result in multiple cascading changes to ecosystems, including promoting diverse assemblages of species, restoring lost guilds, such as scavengers, and restoration of keystone habitats, such as wadi vegetation.

NEOM Nature Reserve aims to restore the richness and abundance of top predators, supported by sustainable prey populations, to catalyze ecosystem restoration. Presently, the native larger terrestrial vertebrate faunal assemblage is weighted heavily towards mesopredators and small mammals (wolves and ibex are exceptions). Rewilding programs aim to restore vertebrate assemblages that function more like estimated ‘natural’ faunal assemblages with more species and numbers of larger predators, larger herbivores, and diverse scavengers. These faunal elements will make up more of the animal biomass and help develop more complex and resilient food webs.

NEOM Nature Reserve has reintroduced and released Arabian oryx, sand gazelle, Arabian gazelle, Nubian ibex, Cape hare, rock hyrax, and red-necked ostrich in three core rewilding zones to date. With the removal of intensive livestock grazing, vegetation has rebounded dramatically, setting the stage for rewilding of not only larger vertebrates, but also birds, reptiles, small mammals, invertebrates, and plants and the ecological processes they are a part of.

Larger Vertebrate Surveys

Camera-Trap Surveys Complement Other Wildlife Survey Methods

Terrestrial vertebrate surveys are key tool for protected area managers and restoration specialists to track changes in faunal assemblages over time and space and ‘rewilding’, in general. This survey has demonstrated the effectiveness of camera-trapping as one method for monitoring medium-to-large mammals (and cursorial birds and larger lizards) within the reserve. This is highlighted by the detection of the six small carnivores (as well as several larger cursorial bird species) that are frequently missed or grouped together at a familial level in analyses of line transect and recce surveys. The cryptic and shy nature, rarity, or nocturnal activity of such species makes them commonly missed or not targeted in transect surveys (Silveira et al. 2003, Tobler 2008, Nakashima 2015). Camera-trap surveys record a much greater proportion of the larger vertebrate fauna than do line transect and recce surveys that are best-suited for gathering data (direct observations and

sign) for larger-bodied species that leave noticeable sign, such as nests and dung (Walters 2010, Bahaa-el-din et al. 2015, Nakashima 2015). Thus, the overall ‘intactness’ status of the larger cursorial vertebrate fauna within a protected area can be effectively estimated using camera-trap surveys (see Box 2).

Box 2. Recommendations to Restore the Larger Terrestrial Vertebrate Fauna

NEOM Nature Reserve recommends the following actions to protect, restore, and manage larger terrestrial vertebrates:

1. Effective control of livestock grazing and hunting is critical to protect and restore wildlife populations.
2. Top predators, such as cheetah, caracal, and Arabian leopard, should be returned to these ecosystems over time, requiring protection from hunting, land to roam, and abundant prey.
3. Rewilding efforts should be supported and expanded according to the NEOM Nature Reserve Rewilding Strategy.
4. Wildlife crossing points of highways should be designed and operated to be wildlife friendly to reduce collisions of wildlife and vehicles.
5. Camera-trap surveys should continue to (i) search for Arabian leopard and caracal, (ii) identify and assess effectiveness of key wildlife corridors and highway crossing points, and (iii) assess the impacts of visitors and other human activities, (iv) assess the impacts of infrastructure and other developments on wildlife, habitats, and ecological processes, (v) measure the effectiveness of conservation interventions, and (vi) track the conservation status of the NEOM Nature Reserve through long-term camera-trap surveys in established Long-Term Ecological Monitoring Sites (16) every 5 years along with 8 other randomly selected sites using standard methods to monitor for larger terrestrial vertebrates (Fig. 3).
6. Test Artificial Intelligence tools for first-cut filtering of camera-trap images for efficient target identification.

Role of Vertebrate Surveys in Protected Area Management

Future larger terrestrial vertebrate surveys within the reserve are recommended to gain further baseline data on medium-to-large mammal distribution and abundance. Such surveys can also provide data to help answer several important and outstanding questions and challenges related to wildlife monitoring for the Nature Reserve:

1. **Close tracking of the status of NEOM Nature Reserve’s vulnerable species** – Close tracking of vulnerable or keystone species, such as larger cat species, Arabian oryx, and sand cats is required to effectively manage populations and track the progress of rewilding and connectivity

restoration efforts. Camera-trap surveys, for example, are reliable at providing direct confirmation of the presence of species and threats. Well-designed surveys, complemented, at times, by other survey methods, can provide confident estimations of population size and trajectory. Understanding the strengths and limitations of each survey method is important to assess the cost-effectiveness of different wildlife monitoring strategies.

2. Identifying Refugia within the NEOM Nature Reserve for Wildlife – Camera traps can provide direct and supporting evidence as to whether factors, such as habitat type, terrain, disturbance, and distance from infrastructure influence larger vertebrate distribution and abundance within the reserve. Some areas within the Nature Reserve may have conditions that enable certain wildlife populations to find refuge from disturbance or find favorable for wildlife movement. Camera-trap surveys can provide data that confirms any such patterns. They can also help determine if highway crossing mitigations are effective for facilitating safe wildlife movement in crossing hotspots.

3. Attribution of Conservation Impacts to Conservation Actions – Though it remains challenging to attribute changes in wildlife metrics to management activity (Ferraro & Pattanayak 2000, Sutherland et al. 2004, Plumptre et al. 2014, Dhanjal-Adams et al. 2015, Critchlow et al. 2016), camera-trap survey data can provide cost-effective and important information on the status of the NEOM Nature Reserve’s megafauna as a whole and can help highlight candidate areas within the reserve or species and guilds deserving of increased management action.

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Institutional Review Board Statement: All surveys were conducted in accordance with the Guide for the Implementing Regulations of the Law of Ethics of Research on Living Creatures (KSA National Committee of BioEthics – Third Edition) and, for surveys conducted by KAUST were conducted under the KAUST Beacon Development’s active research protocol and permit (22IACUC02) approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (the IACUC). NEOM and its contractors follow the guidelines outlined above.

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Appendix A – Camera-Trap Localities & Dates

Table A1. NEOM Nature Reserve Survey camera-trap locality details (199 camera traps).

Public

Survey #	General location	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation m	Deploy date mm/dd/year	Last camera event date mm/dd/year	Trap Nights	LTEM Grid Cell Number, if relevant	Major Ecosystem Type - C coastal, M mountain, H Hisma, HA Harrat	Landform - SP sand plain, GP gravel plain, SW sandy wadi, RW rocky wadi, RO rocky, GH gravel hills	Surveyor - NR = Nature Reserve, KBD = KAUST, NEV = NEDM Environment
1	Al Sourah	27.981996	35.522821	199	5/4/2021	5/23/2021	6		C	SP	NR
2	Al Sourah	27.934606	35.524712	201	5/6/2021	5/13/2021	7		C	SP	NR
3	Al Sourah	27.97817	35.52098	197	5/4/2021	5/23/2021	19		C	SP	NR
4	Al Sourah	27.9053	35.43672	183	3/10/2021	3/16/2021	6		C	RW	NR
5	Al Sourah	28.03092	35.58524	273	6/3/2022	8/5/2022	63		C	RO	NR
6	Al Sourah	27.992	35.606	279	5/5/2021	5/23/2023	748		C	SP	NR
7	Al Sourah	27.941292	35.587131	267	1/1/2019	1/9/2019	8		C	SP	NR
8	Al Sourah	27.99534	35.51799	234	5/4/2021	5/23/2021	19		C	SW	NR
9	Al Sourah	27.94471	35.57258	306	5/14/2021	5/23/2021	9		C	SP	NR
10	Al Sourah	27.98207	35.623196	318	3/28/2021	5/5/2021	38		C	RW	NR
11	Al Sourah	27.9768	35.5401	211	5/14/2021	5/23/2021	9		C	SP	NR
12	Al Sourah	27.9285	35.48164	166	5/6/2021	5/23/2021	17		C	SP	NR
13	Al Sourah	28.01588	35.59807	254	5/12/2021	5/23/2021	11		C	GP	NR
14	Al Sourah	28.0006	35.57174	259	5/11/2021	5/23/2021	12		C	SP	NR
15	Al Sourah	27.99659	35.64324	343	2/22/2021	5/5/2021	72		M	RW	NR
16	Al Sourah	27.98187	35.48402	195	5/4/2021	5/23/2021	19		C	SP	NR
17	Al Sourah	27.93235	35.4444	162	5/5/2021	5/23/2021	18		C	SP/RO	NR
18	Al Sourah	28.03091	35.58524	273	2/23/2021	4/5/2021	41		C	SP/RO	NR
19	Ataqan	29.14423	35.47918	1423	2/8/2021	6/14/2021	126		M	RW	NR
20	Ataqan	29.19234	35.42255	1217	2/9/2021	5/17/2023	827		H	RW	NR
21	Ataqan	29.19005	35.40227	1113	4/6/2021	5/17/2023	771		H	RW	NR
22	Ataqan	29.189959	35.402093	1111	2/9/2021	4/6/2021	56		H	RW	NR
23	Ataqan Wadi Ayyad	29.18814	35.42864	1180	7/19/2023	2/20/2024	216		H	SW	NR
24	Ataqan Wadi Ayyad	29.178861	35.406156	1152	7/19/2023	1/7/2024	172		H	RW	NR
25	Ataqan Wadi Ayyad	29.193131	35.418381	1149	7/19/2023	2/20/2024	216		H	RW	NR
26	Ataqan Wadi Ayyad	29.122561	35.419211	1145	7/19/2023	2/20/2024	216		H	RO	NR
27	Ataqan Wadi Ayyad	29.18826	35.42869	1165	7/19/2023	2/20/2024	216		H	SW	NR
28	Ataqan Wadi Ayyad	29.175428	35.414833	1163	7/19/2023	2/20/2024	216		H	SW	NR
29	Ataqan	29.1575992	35.4048805	1290	4/7/2023	10/15/2023	191	627	H	SW	KBD
30	Ataqan	29.11879	35.3667119	1222	4/7/2023	6/14/2023	68	627	H	SW	KBD
31	Ataqan	29.0908368	35.3856126	1189	4/7/2023	4/21/2023	14		H	GP	KBD
32	Ataqan Wadi Ayyad	29.089239	35.38821	1175	6/14/2023	10/17/2023	125		H	RO	KBD
33	Ataqan	29.09269	35.365984	1272	4/7/2023	6/14/2023	68	627	H	GP	KBD
34	Ataqan Wadi Ayyad	29.0922616	35.3667409	1271	6/14/2023	10/17/2023	125	627	H	RO	KBD
35	Al Suru	28.4275966	35.4897299	1202	4/4/2023	10/19/2023	198	404	M	GH	KBD
36	Al Suru	28.4911157	35.446122	1310	4/4/2023	6/12/2023	69	404	M	RO	KBD

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37	Al Suru	28.491235	35.446111	1311	6/12/2023	10/19/2023	129	404	M	GP	KBD
38	Al Suru	28.4851309	35.4748848	1280	4/4/2023	10/19/2023	198	404	M	RO	KBD
39	Al Suru	28.454453	35.4529295	1244	4/4/2023	10/19/2023	198	404	M	GP	KBD
40	Bajdah WR	28.636688	35.723616	1265	5/28/2024	7/3/2024	36		H	SW	NR
41	Bajdah WR	28.63668	35.72408	1267	6/4/2024	6/15/2024	9		H	SW	NR
42	Bajdah	28.5347743	35.771564	1153	4/3/2023	10/25/2023	205	436	H	SP	KBD
43	Bajdah	28.5681938	35.7767622	1173	4/3/2023	10/25/2023	205	436	H	RO	KBD
44	Bajdah	28.54136	35.82912	991	4/3/2023	6/7/2023	65	436	H	SP	KBD
45	Bajdah	28.56211	35.815145	1070	6/7/2023	10/25/2023	140	436	H	RO	KBD
46	Harrat	28.0614641	36.4900508	987	3/30/2023	10/23/2023	207	276	HA	GP	KBD
47	Harrat	28.0448865	36.4826225	1022	3/30/2023	10/23/2023	207	276	HA	RO	KBD
48	Harrat	28.0286846	36.4727142	1059	3/30/2023	10/22/2023	207	276	HA	RO	KBD
49	Harrat	27.9999621	36.4652285	1107	3/30/2023	6/11/2023	73	276	HA	RO	KBD
50	Jibal al Lawz	28.73282	35.28578	1179	2/23/2021	5/6/2022	437		M	RO	NR
51	Jibal al Lawz	28.76599	35.40443	1475	2/21/2021	7/27/2022	521		M	RO	NR
52	Jibal al Lawz	28.58608	35.2836	892	6/16/2023	10/15/2023	121	458	M	RO	KBD
53	Jibal al Lawz	28.601907	35.28939	957	6/17/2023	10/13/2023	118	458	M	GP	KBD
54	Jibal al Lawz	28.612181	35.269998	857	6/17/2023	10/13/2023	118	458	M	RW	KBD
55	Jibal al Lawz	28.618425	35.253145	806	6/17/2023	10/13/2023	118	458	M	GP	KBD
56	Jabal Sader	28.02464	35.66891	441	2/28/2021	4/10/2021	41		C	SW	NR
57	Jabal Shar	27.62372	35.70033	273	1/12/2020	3/15/2020	63		C	GP	NR
207	Jabal Shar	27.62047	35.70456	280	3.16.2021	3/30/2022	379		C	RW	NR
58	Jabal Shar	27.70625303	35.71637303	267	1/19/2021	3/15/2021	55		C	RW	NR
59	Jabal Shar	27.60279	35.7445	327	1/12/2021	4/17/2021	95		C	SW	NR
60	Jabal Shar	27.70353056	35.7207305	249	1/19/2021	10/14/2021	268		M	RW	NR
61	Jabal Shar	27.67519	35.77766	325	1/19/2021	3/15/2021	55		C	RW	NR
62	Jabal Shar	27.62309	35.70953	322	1/12/2021	3/16/2021	56		C	SW	NR
63	Jabal Shar	27.61446	35.73982	350	1/14/2021	3/28/2022	438		C	SW	NR
64	Jabal Shar	27.64246	35.68049	289	1/12/2021	3/15/2021	62		C	SW	NR
65	Jabal Shar	27.614732	35.740561	353	1/12/2021	3/16/2021	63		C	RW	NR
66	Jabal Shar	27.62954	35.69171	263	3/16/2021	3/30/2022	339		C	RW	NR
67	Jabal Shar	27.64212602	35.67568702	278	1/12/2021	3/16/2021	62		C	RW	NR
68	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.224975	35.505797	648	1/3/2021	2/13/2021	41		C	SW	NR
69	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.2427	35.50406	672	2/2/2021	11/25/2021	295		C	RO	NR
70	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.20017	35.52238	675	2/4/2021	11/24/2021	293		C	RW	NR
71	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.20433	35.51371	602	2/3/2021	7/9/2021	156		C	RO	NR
72	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.21038	35.54066	676	3/11/2021	11/23/2021	257		C	RW	NR
73	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.21063	35.54095	676	12/14/2020	2/21/2021	69		C	RW	NR
74	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.15157	35.49197	457	3/12/2021	11/24/2021	256		M	RW	NR
75	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.17782	35.49485	495	3/12/2021	11/24/2021	256		M	RW	NR

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76	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.177807	35.49477	495	12/25/2020	3/12/2021	77		M	RW	NR
77	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.2421	35.531	866	12/14/2020	11/25/2021	346		M	RW	NR
78	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.16078	35.57312	904	12/15/2020	3/12/2021	87		M	SW	NR
79	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.16064	35.57334	913	3/12/2021	4/7/2021	26		M	RO	NR
80	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.23446	35.52949	757	12/14/2020	3/28/2022	469		M	SW	NR
81	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.19077	35.55685	947	12/15/2020	11/24/2021	344		M	RW	NR
83	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.16209403	35.49153602	495	12/25/2020	3/12/2021	77		M	RW	NR
84	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.10847	35.55441	312	12/23/2020	11/22/2021	334		M	RW	NR
85	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.17876999	35.56380596	826	12/15/2020	3/12/2021	87		M	SW	NR
86	Jabal ash Shiyati	28.16588	35.531361	1033	9/20/2022	3/29/2023	190		M	SW	NEV
87	Jabal Thaghab	28.812715	34.959791	1069	6/18/2023	10/14/2023	118	510	M	RW	KBD
88	Jabal Thaghab	28.756645	34.988339	908	6/18/2023	7/20/2023	32	510	M	GH	KBD
89	Jabal Thaghab	28.829987	34.986851	1204	6/18/2023	10/14/2023	118	510	M	RO	KBD
90	Jabal az Zuduh	28.38626	35.24001	493	2/20/2021	1/26/2022	340		M	SP	NR
91	Jibal al Lawz	28.636997	35.33311	2140	2/7/2024	3/13/2024	35		M	RO	NEV
92	Jibal al Lawz	28.643146	35.333907	2119	2/7/2024	3/12/2024	35		M	RO	NEV
95	Jibal al Lawz	28.66099	35.295251	2298	2/11/2024	3/25/2024	43		M	RO	NEV
96	Jibal al Lawz	28.663412	35.335067	1976	2/11/2024	3/26/2024	44		M	RO	NEV
97	Jibal al Lawz	28.66942	35.327746	1811	2/9/2024	3/28/2024	48		M	RO	NEV
98	Mneifa	28.3121548	35.1600092	204	4/8/2023	10/12/2023	187	344	C	SP	KBD
99	Mneifa	28.3052538	35.1664063	229	4/8/2023	10/12/2023	187	344	C	RO	KBD
100	Mneifa	28.3226246	35.1100926	157	6/13/2023	10/11/2023	120	344	C	SP	KBD
101	Mneifa	28.2993054	35.1102736	125	4/8/2023	6/13/2023	66	344	C	SP	KBD
102	Ras Alshaykh Humayd	28.1328531	34.6303766	24	4/9/2023	6/15/2023	67	282	C	SP	KBD
103	Ras Alshaykh Humayd	28.13265	34.629438	27	6/15/2023	10/12/2023	119	282	C	SW	KBD
104	Ras Alshaykh Humayd	28.1627186	34.6388498	20	4/9/2023	10/12/2023	186	282	C	SP	KBD
105	Ras Alshaykh Humayd	28.0859467	34.6278913	19	4/9/2023	10/12/2023	186	282	C	SP	KBD
106	Ras Alshaykh Humayd	28.1041132	34.5991878	18	4/9/2023	9/23/2023	167	282	C	SP	KBD
107	Ruwafa	27.793109	36.160603	1220	3/29/2023	4/23/2023	25	188	H	RO	KBD
108	Ruwafa	27.794509	36.160272	1221	6/8/2023	10/24/2023	138	188	H	RO	KBD
109	Ruwafa	27.8041342	36.1599803	1201	3/29/2023	10/24/2023	209	188	H	RO	KBD
110	Ruwafa	27.7981094	36.129413	1195	4/1/2023	10/24/2023	190	188	H	RO	KBD
111	Ruwafa	27.7735782	36.1179608	1210	3/29/2023	10/23/2023	208	188	H	RO	KBD
112	Sayr al Kharaj	28.4088706	34.9000155	492	4/10/2023	10/10/2023	183	369	C	GH	KBD
113	Sayr al Kharaj	34.85445	28.40903	505	4/10/2023	10/11/2023	184	369	C	SW	KBD
114	Sayr al Kharaj	28.3498993	34.8468956	221	4/10/2023	10/11/2023	184	369	C	GH	KBD
115	Sayr al Kharaj	28.383217	34.8797301	315	4/10/2023	10/11/2023	184	369	C	SW	KBD
116	Abu Haraq Bajdah Hisma	28.57176	35.737604	1255	3/12/2024	4/19/2024	38		H	SW	NR
117	Wadi al 'lmg N border	29.28739	35.364749	1006	10/23/2023	5/27/2024	217		H	SW	NR

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118	Wadi al 'Img N border	29.229846	35.385897	1183	10/23/2023	5/27/2024	217		H	RW	NR
119	Wadi al 'Img N border	29.22980256	35.38527087	1177	10/23/2023	5/27/2024	217		H	RW	NR
120	Wadi al 'Img N border	29.271048	35.288409	848	10/23/2023	5/27/2024	217		H	SP	NR
121	Wadi al 'Img N border	29.278628	35.37538	1089	10/23/2023	4/18/2024	178		H	SW	NR
122	Wadi al 'Img N border	29.27961	35.375801	1056	10/23/2023	4/6/2024	166		H	SW	NR
123	Wadi al Jamlli al Jamm - Jabal ad Dibbagh	27.85035	35.65301	372	1/16/2024	4/26/2024	101		M	RO	NR
124	Wadi al Jamlli al Jamm - Jabal ad Dibbagh	27.848295	35.654593	402	1/16/2024	4/26/2024	101		M	RO	NR
125	Wadi al Jamlli al Jamm - Jabal ad Dibbagh	27.8489654	35.6558138	397	1/16/2024	4/26/2024	101		M	RO	NR
126	Wadi al Kahali	28.024738	35.668956	441	4/10/2021	1/19/2022	284		M	SW	NR
127	Wadi al Lawz	28.56277778	35.54694444	1298	1/1/2024	1/9/2024	8		M	RO	NR
128	Wadi al Lawz a	28.706387	35.267778	1392	3/2/2024	3/27/2024	25		M	RO	
129	Wadi al Lawz b	28.70638889	35.26777778	1392	3/2/2024	3/27/2024	25		M	RO	NR
130	Wadi al Lawz	28.70777778	35.27305556	1700	1/1/2024	1/25/2024	24		M	RO	NR
131	Wadi al Qishabariyah - SW Jabal ad Dibbagh	27.81141	35.68233	477	1/5/2024	2/20/2024	46		M	RO	NR
132	Wadi al Kahali - Al Sourah	27.9233556	35.5564373	233	4/6/2023	10/16/2023	193	237	C	RO	KBD
133	Wadi al Kahali - Al Sourah	27.933773	35.518793	193	6/19/2023	10/16/2023	119	237	C	RO	KBD
134	Wadi al Kahali - Al Sourah	27.9336127	35.5190502	194	4/6/2023	6/19/2023	74	237	C	SP	KBD
135	Wadi al Kahali - Al Sourah	27.9888181	35.5146058	219	6/19/2023	10/16/2023	119	237	C	SP	KBD
137	Wadi al Kahali - Al Sourah	27.9938453	35.5599523	253	4/6/2023	10/16/2023	193	237	C	SW	KBD
139	Wadi Aynunah	28.2723	35.3678	414	2/11/2021	1/11/2022	334		C	GH	NR
140	Wadi Aynunah	28.21756	35.37809	345	2/10/2021	1/8/2022	332		C	RW	KBD
141	Wadi Aynunah	28.0670931	35.218753	62	4/8/2023	10/16/2023	191		C	RW	NR
142	Wadi Dabr	28.97559	35.004734	1064	4/9/2023	5/31/2023	52		M	GP	NR
143	Aqaba Plain	28.9178	34.87331	139	4/9/2023	5/31/2023	52		C	GP	NR
144	Wadi Dabr	28.98602	35.04009	973	4/9/2023	5/31/2023	52		M	GP	NR
145	Wadi Dabr	28.97568	35.04695	1064	4/9/2023	4/21/2023	12		M	GP	NR
146	Aqaba Plain	28.9134	34.90012	308	4/9/2023	5/30/2023	51		C	GP	NR
147	Wadi Dabr	29.046751	35.017012	901	4/10/2023	6/16/2023	67	595	C	GP	KBD
148	Wadi Dabr	29.022243	35.006095	777	6/16/2023	10/15/2023	121	595	M	SW	KBD
149	Wadi Dabr	29.04676	35.01702	901	6/16/2023	9/2/2023	78	595	M	SP	KBD
150	Wadi Dabr	29.0809368	35.055218	751	4/10/2023	10/14/2023	187	595	M	RO	KBD
151	Wadi Dabr	29.0638253	35.0255825	928	4/10/2023	10/15/2023	188	595	M	RW	KBD
152	Wadi Ghuwayl	28.197311	35.874744	1057	4/1/2023	6/9/2023	69	325	H	SP	KBD
153	Wadi Ghuwayl	28.1969096	35.8753041	1068	4/3/2023	6/9/2023	67	325	H	SP	KBD
154	Wadi Ghuwayl	28.1692348	35.8702088	1090	4/1/2023	6/9/2023	60	325	H	RO	KBD

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155	Wadi Ghuwayl	28.2455801	35.844596	1037	4/10/2023	10/24/2023	197	325	H	GP	KBD
156	Wadi Habib N J Zuduh	28.357217	35.274757	950	11/27/2023	2/17/2024	82		M	RO	NR
157	Wadi Habib N J Zuduh	28.361514	35.279357	870	11/27/2023	4/19/2024	144		M	RO	NR
158	Wadi Habib N J Zuduh	28.357187	35.283928	745	11/27/2023	4/18/2024	143		M	RW	NR
159	Wadi Habib N Zuduh	28.35834	35.28489	714	11/27/2023	4/18/2024	143		M	RO	NR
160	Wadi Hrp Mneifa	28.337468	35.165827	231	7/29/2022	9/1/2022	34		C	SW	NR
161	Wadi Hrp Mneifa	28.3467	35.177795	289	4/12/2023	11/5/2023	207		C	SW	NR
162	Wadi Hrp Mneifa	28.344559	35.173316	292	4/12/2023	11/5/2023	207		C	SW	NR
163	Wadi Huwayy	28.517499	35.342258	1182	11/28/2020	1/8/2021	41		M	SW	NR
164	Wadi Kulayb	28.88144	34.962009	763	11/9/2023	6/3/2024	207		M	RO	NR
165	Wadi Kulayb	28.879924	34.968628	771	11/9/2023	6/3/2024	207		M	GH	NR
166	Wadi Kulayb	28.880736	34.970211	797	11/9/2023	6/6/2024	210		M	RW	NR
167	Wadi Kulayb	28.883175	34.987561	818	11/9/2023	4/4/2024	147		M	SW	NR
168	Wadi Kulayb	28.884517	34.965099	740	11/9/2023	1/10/2024	62		M	RO	NR
169	Wadi Kulayb	28.885953	34.995019	918	11/9/2023	6/6/2024	210		M	RO	NR
170	Wadi Kulayb	28.887453	35.002339	936	11/9/2023	6/6/2024	210		M	RW	NR
171	Wadi Sayyid	28.92151	35.11129	934	4/9/2023	5/31/2023	52		M	SW	NR
172	Wadi Sadr	27.916096	35.730138	438	4/5/2023	6/19/2023	75	211	C	GP	KBD
173	Wadi Sadr	27.877765	35.678742	442	5/17/2023	10/14/2023	150	211	M	SW	KBD
174	Wadi Sadr	27.9066634	35.6683748	388	4/4/2023	6/18/2023	75	211	M	SW	KBD
175	Wadi Sadr	27.9033626	35.7039938	419	4/4/2023	10/15/2023	194	211	M	RO	KBD
176	Wadi Surr	27.70858056	35.68931111	203	1/19/2021	4/28/2022	464		C	RW	NR
177	Wadi Tayyib lsm	28.56684599	34.80681801	353	12/20/2020	3/24/2021	94		M	SW	NR
178	Wadi Tayyib lsm	28.566854	34.806821	354	11/3/2020	11/25/2020	22		M	SW	NR
179	Wadi Tayyib lsm	28.571428	34.826477	216	12/20/2020	4/1/2021	102		M	SW	NR
180	Wadi Tayyib lsm	28.571385	34.821895	320	11/3/2020	11/11/2020	8		M	SW	NR
181	Wadi Tayyib lsm	28.57172	34.82387	196	11/5/2020	11/10/2020	5		M	SW	NR
182	Wadi Tayyib lsm	28.57138596	34.81895199	216	11/3/2020	11/25/2020	22		M	SW	NR
183	Wadi Tayyib lsm	28.57029	34.82042	196	12/20/2020	4/1/2021	102		M	SW	NR
184	Wadi Tayyib lsm	28.572542	34.824153	204	12/20/2020	4/1/2021	102		M	SW	NR
185	Wadi Tayyib lsm	28.574666	34.8254	229	11/3/2020	11/25/2020	22		M	SW	NR
186	Wadi Thurf	29.0039058	35.9023574	840	4/2/2023	10/22/2023	203	605	H	SP	KBD
187	Wadi Thurf	29.008967	35.8935907	848	4/2/2023	10/26/2023	207	605	H	SW	KBD
188	Wadi Thurf	29.0106124	35.869875	884	4/2/2023	10/26/2023	207	605	H	RO	KBD
189	Wadi Thurf	29.010686	35.8554158	930	4/2/2023	10/26/2023	207	605	H	RO	KBD
190	Wadi Umm Ararah	28.229572	35.57458	1288	6/14/2022	9/3/2022	80		M	SW	NR
191	Wadi Umm Ararah	28.22966	35.574755	1289	6/15/2022	6/28/2022	13		M	SW	NR
193	Harrat	28.0114641	36.4900508	387	3/30/2023	6/11/2023	73	276	HA	GP	KBD
194	Harrat	27.999175	36.465305	1119	6/11/2023	10/23/2023	135	276	HA	RO	KBD

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195	Jabal Marshah	28.783056	34.911606	1639	5/11/2023	6/26/2023	46		M	RO	NR
196	Jabal ad Dibbagh	27.865023	35.746216	2045	5/7/2023	11/22/2024	565		M	RO	NR
197	Jabal ad Dibbagh	27.863395	35.745915	2063	5/7/2023	11/22/2024	565		M	RO	NR
198	Jabal Imaiq	29.183201	35.451514	1808	5/10/2023	12/8/2023	20		M	RO	NR
199	Jabal Mahash	29.05471	35.508634	1460	5/10/2023	5/30/2023	20		H	RO	NR
200	Jabal Mahash	29.051467	35.509	1455	5/10/2023	6/11/2023	32		H	RO	NR
203	Jabal az Zuduh	28.318381	35.296732	1884	5/9/2023	7/19/2023	71		M	RO	NR
204	Bajdah WR	28.55604	35.711955	1234	8/7/2024	9/4/2024	28		H	SW	NR
205	Wadi Ghuwayl	28.197353	35.874873	1060	6/9/2023	10/24/2023	137	325	H	SW	KBD
206	Alaqan Wadi Ayyad	29.118849	35.367053	1224	6/14/2023	10/17/2023	125	627	H	GH	NR
NEOM NATURE RESERVE 2025-2026 ADDITIONAL CAMERA-TRAP DEPLOYMENT LOCALITIES											
	Aqaba Range	28.77799	34.84271	688	4/12/2025	9/5/2025	146		M	RO	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.78699	34.83572	208	11/19/2024	2/7/2025	80		M	RW	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.77734	34.84374	751	4/12/2025	9/5/2025	146		M	RO	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.77799	34.84271	739	4/12/2025	9/5/2025	146		M	RO	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.78701	34.83248	150	11/19/2024	2/7/2025	80		M	RW	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.78696	34.83408	184	11/9/2024	2/7/2025	80		M	RW	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.78605	34.83577	241	11/19/2024	2/7/2025	80		M	RW	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.82433	34.85018	219	2/7/2025	4/12/2025	64		M	RO	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.82448	34.85021	205	2/7/2025	4/12/2025	64		M	RW	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.82427	34.85385	233	2/7/2025	4/12/2025	64		M	RO	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.82606	34.84955	169	2/7/2025	4/12/2025	64		M	RW	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.76963	34.84174	365	4/12/2025	9/5/2025	146		M	RO	NR
	Aqaba Range	28.76758	34.83824	280	4/12/2025	9/5/2025	146		M	RO	NR
	NW Jabal Lawz	28.70945	35.27242	1757	5/31/2025	10/1/2025	123		M	RO	NR
	NW Jabal Lawz	28.70765	35.26727	1408	5/31/2025	10/1/2025	123		M	RO	NR
	NW Jabal Lawz	28.70357	35.25445	1071	5/31/2025	10/1/2025	123		M	RO	NR
	Hisma	28.69921	35.86914	1154	2/7/2025	4/24/2025	76		H	RW	NR
	Hisma	28.70058	35.87048	1141	2/7/2025	4/24/2025	76		H	RW	NR
	Al Sourah	27.9818	35.48402	193	11/8/2025	11/22/2025	14		C	SP	NR
	Al Suru	28.65424	35.47167	1367	9/11/2025	11/11/2025	61		M	RO	NR
	Al Suru	28.65586	35.47838	1322	9/11/2025	11/11/2025	61		M	RW	NR
	Al Suru	28.65651	35.47312	1405	9/11/2025	11/11/2025	61		M	RO	NR
	Hisma	28.70058	35.87048	1139	2/7/2025	4/24/2025	76		H	RW	NR
	NW J Lawz	28.7092	35.27014	1615	5/31/2025	10/1/2025	123		M	RO	NR
	NW J Lawz	28.70245	35.26181	1264	5/31/2025	10/1/2025	123		M	RO	NR
	Aqaba	28.77112	34.84137	379	4/12/2025	9/5/2025	146		M	RO	NR
	Hisma	28.70060	35.86933	1138	2/7/2025	4/24/2025	76		H	RW	NR
	Al Suru	28.65688	35.475	1332	9/11/2025	11/11/2025	61		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.67005	35.74235	570	10/31/2025	11/14/2025	14		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.66979	35.74227	580	10/31/2025	1/13/2026	74		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.66011	35.73528	873	10/31/2025	11/14/2025	14		M	RW	NR

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	Jabal Shar	27.65582	35.73404	1028	10/31/2025	1/13/2026	74		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.65658	35.73481	1051	10/31/2025	1/13/2026	74		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.67115	35.74434	558	10/31/2025	1/13/2026	74		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.65534	35.756	997	11/14/2025	1/27/2026	74		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.6485	35.75593	972	11/14/2025	1/27/2026	74		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.64992	35.75704	856	11/14/2025	1/27/2026	74		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.65071	35.7594	804	11/14/2025	1/27/2026	74		M	RW	NR
	Jabal Shar	27.65444	35.76641	588	11/14/2025	1/27/2026	74		M	RW	NR

Table A2. Further description of location, habitats of KAUST/BDC camera traps in LTEM sites. These camera localities are in Table A1, but more details are provided here for this subset.

Survey Square No	Survey reference ID	Location and Description	Habitats
Long Term Monitoring (LTM) Squares			
1	188*	In the far south of the Hisma Plateau, bordering on Harrat Al Raha to the north-east and the Midyan Mountains to the west and south. Most of the site lies between about 1,100 m and 1,300 m, with the higher points situated on buttes. Only in the far south-west towards the Midyan Mountains does the land fall off to just below 800 m.	Sand sheets and dunes with <i>Haloxylon salicornicum</i> was dominant. Also with sandstone buttes and shallow wadis. Small areas of sandstone pavement.
2*	211*	Towards the south-western part of NEOM in the Midyan Mountains. It includes Jebel Dubbagh, an alkali granite dome and at 2,280 m, one of the highest mountains in NEOM. It is certainly one of the most important mountains from a biodiversity perspective. Apart from a broad wadi in the north and north-west, the landscape of the Square is mainly mountainous.	Calc-alkaline slopes from 250m to above 1500m. Also wadis with distinct tree cover associated with slopes.
3	237	On an extensive plain at the base of the western edge of the Midyan Mountains. The elevation of the plain, which occupies by far the largest part of the Square and runs generally from north-east to south-west, ranges from 170 to 260 m. The low craggy hills dotted along the margins of the plain reach 380 m asl.	Sand sheets with <i>Haloxylon salicornicum</i> with alluvial plains and foothills of mountains.
4	261	On the coastal and near-coastal plain towards the north of the Red Sea in the eastern part of Sharma Bay, on the western edge of the Midyan Mountains. Given the location, the elevation ranges from 0 to a maximum of about 130 m in the low-lying hills in the north. The central part of the Square includes the mouth of Wadi Sharma, a major wadi consisting of several braided channels that runs from the south-east to the sea.	Wadis in coastal situations with scattered halophytic dwarf shrub vegetation and coastal plains.
5	276	On the northern-eastern edge of Harrat Al Raha, where in terms of the surface geology there is a mosaic of sandstones of the Hisma Plateau and the more recent basaltic lavas. These lavas occupy the largest proportion of the Square and due to the nature of the coarse substrate, the terrain is poorly accessible.	Sandstone buttes and dissected tableland of the Hisma Plateau with wadis, slopes and summits of Harrat Al Raha.
6	282	On the far west of NEOM in the northern part of the Ras Al-Sheikh Hamid headland towards the mouth of the Gulf of Aqaba. The landscape is largely flat but locally with low, gravelly hills, presumably derived from severely eroded coral mesas. The elevation ranges from sea-level to about 60 m in the interior.	Coastal plains, gravel sheets, sabhka and coastal cliffs, beaches and mesas.
7	325	On the Hisma Plateau to the south of the Tabuk to Sharma road, characterized by extensive, deep sand sheets that are interspersed with a high density of sandstone buttes. The general terrain is quite flat, with the sand sheets rising within the Square from about 1,020 m to 1,130 m. The buttes rise about 30 m above the surrounding landscape, a few 60 m, and the highest point in the Square reaches 1,150 m.	Weathered sandstone buttes, sandy-gravelly plains and echo dunes of the Hisma Plateau with shallow wadis.
8	344	About 20 km to the south-east of Al Bad on the alluvial plain at the western foot of Jebel Al Zudh. Most of the area is fairly flat to gently undulating. The lowest point is found on the plains at 90 m asl. The higher elevations are associated with the lower slopes of Jebel Al Zudh on the far eastern edge of the Square. These lie mainly below 250 m.	Lower Midyan slopes with scattered trees, alluvial plains and wadis in association with mountains and more open terrain.
Long Term Monitoring (LTM) Squares			
Survey Square No	Survey reference ID	Location and Description	Habitats
9	369	To the south-west of Al Bad and is dominated by an area of low mountains dissected by narrow wadis and including several extensive wadi plains. The mountains reach 700 m in the far north-east at the highest point, but typically 200 to 500 m over most of the area. The substrate of the plains consists to a large extent of fine to coarse gravels, locally cobbles. Finer gravels predominate in the actual wadi channels.	Lower Midyan slopes with scattered trees, alluvial plains and wadis in association with mountains and more open terrain.
10	404	In the Midyan Mountains, about 25 km to the south-east of Jebel Al Lawz, characterized by a large alluvial plain with granitic gravel substrate in the northern central part and is otherwise surrounded by mountains. The elevation ranges from about 1,170 m on the plain in the far south-east to just over 1,500 m in the mountains in the south-west.	Mid-high elevation Midyan Mountains with wadis and alluvial plains with shrub vegetation.
11	436*	On the Hisma Plateau just over 20 km to the north of the Tabuk to Sharma road. It is characterized by extensive, deep sand sheets that are interspersed with a high density of impressive sandstone buttes.	Sandstone buttes and dissected table land with sand sheets, low dunes and shallow wadis on the Hisma Plateau
12	458	In the Jebel Al Lawz range; most of the Square is situated above 1,000 m, with large sections of the north and east exceeding 1,500 m and reaching 2,420 m in the north-east. Most of the northern section consists of syenogranite, with smaller patches of monzogranite interspersed. These are typical calc-alkaline rocks. In the south, noticeably darker, metamorphosed volcanic rocks prevail.	High elevation calc-alkaline slopes with mountain wadis and springs and some pools.
13	510*	Situated in a mountainous area close to the Gulf of Aqaba, comprises high mountains with several broad wadis. The Square also contains the lower and parts of the upper slopes of both Jebel Thaghb (central-north) and Jebel Marshah (south-west). The peaks of both mountains lie about 0.75 km outside of the Square, respectively. A further mountain peak in the centre of the Square reaches 1,730 m and is the highest point in the Square. The terrain in most of the Square lies above 900 m.	Low to high elevation Midyan mountain slopes with alluvial plains
14	595	In the Midyan Mountains in the north-west. The elevation ranges from 700 m in the far north-east, to 1,185 m in the far north-west. Most of the mountains, however, lie below 1,000 m. The south-eastern part of the Square is occupied by an extensive gravel plain ("wadi plain"), where numerous wadis merge onto the plain from the south-east.	Low to high elevation Midyan mountain slopes with alluvial plains
15	605	In the northern central section of the Hisma Plateau with sandy substrate with extensive patches of gravel. Fairly low butte complexes occur in both the north-west and south-west of the Square. The terrain is flat throughout, with the plains and sand sheets lying between roughly 810 to 950 m asl, and the highest points on the buttes to 975 m, although typically much lower.	Sand sheets and dunes with <i>Haloxylon salicornicum</i> . Also with sandstone buttes and shallow wadis. Small areas of sandstone pavement.
16	627*	In the north-west around Alaqa and includes part of the eastern edge of Midyan Mountains with the eastern part of the Square incorporating a section of the Hisma Plateau with its extensive sand sheets and buttes. The elevation is between 1,070 and 1,600 m, with the highest point found in the Midyan Mountains in the south of the Square) and the lowest point on the sand sheets in the far north.	Mountain slopes, sand sheets and dunes with <i>Haloxylon salicornicum</i> . Also with sandstone buttes and shallow wadis.

Table A3. Camera-trap localities (232 total) and dates for NEOM development sector surveys (courtesy I Walshingham-Simms & Chris Boland).

Camera ID	Date set	Date retrieved	Latitude	Longitude
1	9/13/2021	9/21/2021	28.315412	34.9187
6	9/15/2022	9/20/2022	28.46623	35.101317
12	10/8/2022	10/17/2022	28.45516	35.101693
14	10/22/2022	11/5/2022	28.447662	35.095276
12	4/27/2023	5/2/2023	28.487152	35.099652
1	8/23/2023	9/6/2023	28.126397	35.490934
3	9/9/2023	9/16/2023	28.393529	34.855066
4	9/15/2023	9/22/2023	28.165004	35.185902
6	9/22/2023	10/5/2023	28.165482	35.185553
10	10/3/2023	10/13/2023	28.55318	35.083172
1	3/11/2024	3/25/2024	27.728631	36.02471
2	3/11/2024	3/25/2024	27.671597	36.007067
10	3/11/2024	3/25/2024	27.736519	36.022259
8	3/13/2024	3/25/2024	27.71406	35.95254
1	3/24/2024	4/6/2024	28.33645	34.81411
6	3/25/2024	4/8/2024	27.746885	35.940847
3	3/31/2024	4/14/2024	28.315473	34.918739
4	3/31/2024	4/14/2024	28.208083	34.947287
4	3/31/2024	4/14/2024	28.222684	34.969951
6	3/31/2024	4/14/2024	28.155322	34.96331
6	4/14/2024	4/28/2024	28.455537	35.101302
1	4/20/2024	5/4/2024	27.967566	36.347288
3	4/28/2024	5/12/2024	28.48625	35.113501
3	8/21/2024	8/31/2024	28.049996	36.313478
6	8/26/2024	8/31/2024	27.977727	36.384317
7	8/31/2024	9/15/2024	27.949442	36.382274
10	8/31/2024	9/14/2024	28.308549	35.02232
10A	9/1/2024	9/14/2024	28.073568	36.230883
1	9/14/2024	9/28/2024	28.065802	36.355156
2	9/14/2024	9/28/2024	28.072915	36.328229
8	9/14/2024	9/28/2024	28.025224	36.232548
2A	9/29/2024	10/13/2024	28.504423	35.092268
2B	4/11/2021	4/19/2021	28.455454	35.101097
5	3/28/2023	4/5/2023	28.512965	35.078253
2	10/24/2023	11/2/2023	28.052435	35.868321
5	2/18/2024	3/7/2024	28.165471	35.193559
2	3/3/2024	3/17/2024	28.329502	34.919864
5	3/9/2024	3/23/2024	28.097149	35.655458
8	3/13/2024	3/25/2024	27.769712	35.981306

3	3/17/2024	3/31/2024	28.372861	34.93717
1	3/17/2024	3/31/2024	28.516761	35.09621
10	3/31/2024	4/14/2024	28.505953	35.089511
2	4/6/2024	4/17/2024	28.061325	36.014648
2	4/6/2024	4/20/2024	28.393508	34.885471
10	4/17/2024	5/1/2024	28.053816	36.398564
1	4/17/2024	5/1/2024	27.983876	36.384539
2	4/18/2024	5/2/2024	28.0249322	36.23188
4	4/18/2024	4/30/2024	28.06453	35.783764
2	4/20/2024	5/4/2024	27.891778	36.210665
7	5/1/2024	5/15/2024	28.057641	36.310177
1	5/4/2024	5/16/2024	27.942825	36.261791
2	5/4/2024	5/15/2024	28.331947	34.867837
1D	5/4/2024	5/15/2024	28.356787	34.877998
5	8/21/2024	8/31/2024	28.01938	36.388833
9	9/14/2024	9/28/2024	28.044431	36.233513
1C	9/18/2024	10/3/2024	28.050399	35.877574
3	3/25/2024	4/8/2024	27.701118	36.028174
2	10/11/2021	10/18/2021	28.455395	35.101765
7	9/3/2022	9/7/2022	27.794918	36.210553
5A	9/12/2022	10/5/2024	27.801999	36.145711
7	9/19/2022	9/24/2022	28.325498	34.922445
15	10/22/2022	10/30/2022	28.374616	34.935781
2	3/16/2023	3/22/2023	27.988461	36.658653
4	4/16/2023	4/22/2023	28.049602	35.878848
7	4/22/2023	4/29/2023	28.1204116	35.37059
11	4/26/2023	4/29/2023	28.35734	34.993104
1	9/10/2023	9/17/2023	28.0147	36.218683
6	9/10/2023	9/16/2023	28.38971	35.04953
9	10/10/2023	10/19/2023	28.369734	34.952422
9	3/3/2024	3/17/2024	28.350114	34.945796
1	3/3/2024	3/17/2024	28.254231	34.993991
1	3/9/2024	3/20/2024	27.947762	36.389932
7	3/9/2024	3/20/2024	28.009563	36.395655
3	3/23/2024	4/7/2024	27.866645	36.354811
7	3/24/2024	4/6/2024	28.333471	34.825841
5	3/25/2024	4/8/2024	27.698095	35.990839
4	4/6/2024	4/20/2024	28.352722	34.832524
3	4/7/2024	4/20/2024	27.910319	36.293924
6	4/17/2024	5/1/2024	28.07445	36.320209
1	4/20/2024	5/4/2024	28.380581	34.867405
3	5/1/2024	5/15/2024	28.080701	36.333449
2	5/4/2024	5/16/2024	27.877751	36.338506

4	8/21/2024	8/31/2024	28.059987	36.40901
3	8/25/2024	9/8/2024	28.217537	34.737865
2	8/25/2024	9/8/2024	28.133005	35.468193
4	9/8/2024	9/25/2024	28.074681	35.67319
2C	9/21/2024	10/3/2024	28.019969	36.216391
4	9/22/2024	10/7/2024	28.207321	34.737596
6	10/20/2024	11/3/2024	28.189149	34.743136
5	5/7/2021	5/21/2021	28.319065	34.918294
4	3/17/2024	3/31/2024	28.190747	34.907249
4	4/5/2023	4/13/2023	28.01223	36.2315
2	3/22/2021	3/27/2021	28.318948	34.920213
7	4/6/2023	4/12/2023	28.455549	35.101538
2	3/14/2023	3/21/2023	28.165001	35.185918
2	3/20/2024	4/7/2024	28.177672	34.731031
4	4/20/2024	5/4/2024	27.903835	36.330863
1	4/28/2024	5/12/2024	28.190747	34.947287
4	3/23/2023	3/31/2023	28.191762	34.737102
6	4/15/2023	4/22/2023	28.117581	35.460001
Carcass	9/2/2023	9/6/2023	28.493731	35.057391
14	10/27/2023	11/2/2023	28.435011	35.099755
5	4/6/2024	4/20/2024	28.371123	34.831919
4	4/16/2024	5/2/2024	28.07973	36.233143
3	9/4/2024	9/18/2024	28.095209	35.388224
5	9/18/2024	10/2/2024	28.122703	35.410673
1	3/20/2021	3/22/2021	28.314254	34.920213
3	4/3/2021	4/5/2021	28.322008	35.02059
4	4/25/2021	5/7/2021	28.310783	34.920233
3B	5/3/2021	5/13/2021	28.533973	35.079273
4B	5/11/2021	5/21/2021	28.487986	35.098475
5B	5/13/2021	5/21/2021	28.522898	35.075563
1	9/16/2021	9/25/2021	29.13492	34.954814
2	9/26/2021	10/9/2021	29.098206	34.92764
3	10/10/2021	10/23/2021	29.091463	34.887544
4	10/24/2021	11/4/2021	29.065732	34.920396
1	3/19/2022	3/26/2022	29.103352	34.928716
1	3/22/2022	3/31/2022	28.477072	35.121644
2	3/26/2022	4/2/2022	29.091359	34.888866
2	4/6/2022	4/20/2022	28.315472	34.918713
4	4/23/2022	4/30/2022	29.052379	34.87231
2B	5/3/2022	5/10/2022	28.455392	35.101248
5	9/12/2022	9/19/2022	28.325863	34.917549
2	9/14/2022	9/20/2022	27.906588	35.480035
8	9/20/2022	9/29/2022	28.492636	35.098572

9	9/26/2022	10/1/2022	28.455098	35.101299
10	9/29/2022	10/5/2022	28.507342	35.082409
11	10/5/2022	10/15/2022	28.30836	35.022061
13	10/15/2022	10/22/2022	28.375802	34.939476
4	3/11/2023	3/18/2023	28.222599	35.997464
1	3/11/2023	3/15/2023	28.201206	34.736245
1	3/11/2023	3/18/2023	28.124097	35.417535
1	3/12/2023	3/20/2023	28.534342	35.078524
3	3/15/2023	3/23/2023	28.198738	34.735361
4	3/22/2023	3/30/2023	28.322186	34.91627
1	3/23/2023	4/4/2023	28.374118	34.851391
1	3/25/2023	4/10/2023	28.234871	34.759397
3	3/25/2023	4/1/2023	28.135799	35.337452
6	3/30/2023	4/6/2023	28.312106	34.917522
5	3/31/2023	4/6/2023	28.18722	34.743258
4	4/1/2023	4/9/2023	28.116312	35.387274
2	4/6/2023	4/15/2023	28.236712	36.0178
6	4/6/2023	4/10/2023	28.19043	34.736916
2	4/10/2023	4/27/2023	28.257887	34.696631
7	4/14/2023	4/20/2023	28.187884	34.722224
1	4/15/2023	4/22/2023	28.300895	35.995235
2	4/19/2023	4/27/2023	27.917787	36.286707
8	4/20/2023	4/28/2023	28.192392	34.721926
9	4/21/2023	4/26/2023	28.173085	35.160442
10	4/28/2023	5/4/2023	28.199978	34.720517
2	4/29/2023	5/7/2023	28.37333	35.927876
4	4/29/2023	5/7/2023	28.35689	35.937659
13	4/30/2023	5/9/2023	28.335228	34.936343
11	5/4/2023	5/12/2023	28.201993	34.719078
1	8/21/2023	8/28/2023	28.198573	34.735429
2	8/25/2023	9/1/2023	28.170174	35.194435
2	8/26/2023	9/3/2023	28.31884	34.91832
2	9/2/2023	9/9/2023	28.353062	34.866703
1	9/3/2023	9/10/2023	28.268593	34.69963
4	9/3/2023	9/9/2023	28.30521	34.961169
3	9/4/2023	9/11/2023	28.202196	34.719089
3	9/5/2023	9/12/2023	28.52363	35.04758
2	9/6/2023	9/13/2023	28.119352	35.378026
4	9/16/2023	9/23/2023	28.394511	34.854473
8	9/17/2023	10/3/2023	28.513215	35.078809
5	9/18/2023	10/4/2023	28.1916	34.73708
5	9/18/2023	9/24/2023	28.460167	35.083168
2	9/19/2023	9/27/2023	28.073577	36.091827

5	9/23/2023	9/29/2023	28.404685	34.86954
3	9/28/2023	10/7/2023	28.029402	36.162813
6	9/29/2023	10/6/2023	28.412334	34.888972
4	9/30/2023	10/7/2023	28.040723	35.964211
7	10/2/2023	10/10/2023	28.53257	35.08993
7	10/4/2023	10/12/2023	28.199087	34.736802
8	10/5/2023	10/14/2023	28.167555	35.178425
7	10/6/2023	10/13/2023	28.383141	34.867669
4	10/9/2023	10/16/2023	28.1175816	35.387527
4	10/9/2023	10/14/2023	28.066802	36.019576
12	10/13/2023	10/21/2023	28.364815	35.051583
8	10/13/2023	10/20/2023	28.364088	34.827707
4	10/17/2023	10/23/2023	28.1784378	34.7250604
9	10/17/2023	10/24/2023	28.210702	34.740222
11	10/19/2023	10/27/2023	28.352638	34.987559
9	10/21/2023	10/29/2023	28.334866	34.807849
13	10/23/2023	10/31/2023	28.321473	34.916141
5	10/25/2023	11/2/2023	28.047514	35.9425
4	10/28/2023	11/2/2023	28.110397	35.472419
10	3/3/2024	3/17/2024	28.454741	35.088087
4	3/6/2024	3/20/2024	28.111037	35.418018
1	3/7/2024	3/24/2024	28.000226	36.234266
7	3/7/2024	4/23/2024	27.903825	36.330863
8	3/7/2024	4/23/2024	27.940486	36.329066
9	3/9/2024	3/21/2024	28.03661	36.18437
1	3/9/2024	3/17/2024	28.30581	34.867405
1	3/9/2024	3/17/2024	28.406623	34.86873
2	3/9/2024	3/17/2024	28.396642	34.873247
1	3/10/2024	3/16/2024	28.202194	34.719774
3	3/10/2024	3/16/2024	28.217437	34.737865
5	3/10/2024	3/16/2024	28.198687	34.735336
7	3/10/2024	3/16/2024	28.201154	34.766874
8	3/10/2024	3/16/2024	28.220348	34.758699
9	3/10/2024	3/16/2024	28.242895	34.758699
5	3/20/2024	4/3/2024	28.110642	35.430898
1	3/23/2024	4/4/2024	28.0592	35.94766
7	3/23/2024	4/6/2024	28.125586	35.460598
9	3/25/2024	4/8/2024	27.736253	35.977685
10	4/7/2024	4/21/2024	28.262212	34.788687
4	4/7/2024	4/20/2024	27.956652	36.218107
3	4/7/2024	4/17/2024	28.019477	36.224718
6	4/20/2024	5/4/2024	28.393508	34.885477
9	4/28/2024	5/12/2024	28.22684	34.969951

8	5/2/2024	5/15/2024	28.138962	35.284353
6	5/6/2024	5/18/2024	28.069735	35.804311
1A	8/18/2024	8/31/2024	28.253469	34.987278
1	8/21/2024	9/4/2024	28.111912	35.38711
1A	8/22/2024	9/4/2024	28.047758	36.166738
1A	8/24/2024	9/7/2024	28.368431	34.872236
2A	8/24/2024	9/7/2024	28.341007	34.876994
3A	8/24/2024	9/7/2024	28.343502	34.84803
9	8/25/2024	9/8/2024	28.242895	34.764205
10A	8/25/2024	9/8/2024	28.224883	34.704619
1	8/26/2024	9/3/2024	28.157048	34.830384
2	8/26/2024	9/3/2024	28.181943	34.882659
1B	9/5/2024	9/17/2024	28.070862	35.742057
2B	9/7/2024	9/19/2024	28.05879	35.952228
10	9/21/2024	10/5/2024	28.327152	34.815675
6	9/24/2024	10/9/2024	28.136304	35.485429
7	10/4/2024	10/16/2024	28.149804	35.288569
8	10/9/2024	10/23/2024	28.095231	35.434885
9	10/16/2024	10/30/2024	28.145036	35.333411
10	10/23/2024	11/6/2024	28.088718	35.647188
11	10/30/2024	11/6/2024	28.127533	35.353456

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Appendix C – IUCN Red List Categories & Saudi Arabia National Criteria for High Conservation Priority Species

I. Saudi Arabia National Criteria for High Conservation Priority Species

- Genera, species, or subspecies that are critically endangered, endangered, or vulnerable (globally, regionally, or nationally); taxa which are locally extinct in the wild may be included, provided that there is an NCWCD policy to reintroduce them.
- Genera, species, or subspecies that are endemic to the Arabian Peninsula, the Red Sea, or the Gulf.
- Genera, species, or subspecies of which the conservation of populations within Saudi Arabia is essential to the conservation of the taxon (e.g. near-endemics and migrants for which Saudi Arabia represents a critical range).
- Relict genera, species, or subspecies that are of global, regional, or national significance.
- Genera or species of special ecological importance (i.e. fulfilling a vitally important function in an ecosystem such as providing a key habitat for other species, serving as indicator species, etc).
- Genera of species of significant economic importance.
- Genera or species that serve a “flagship” function (i.e. high-profile species of cultural value, the protection of which will also protect large numbers of other species that share their habit

II. IUCN Red List Categories (IUCN 2024a)

EXTINCT (EX)

A taxon is Extinct when there is no reasonable doubt that the last individual has died. A taxon is presumed Extinct when exhaustive surveys in known and/or expected habitat, at appropriate times (diurnal, seasonal, annual), throughout its historic range have failed to record an individual. Surveys should be over a time frame appropriate to the taxon's life cycle and life form.

EXTINCT IN THE WILD (EW)

A taxon is Extinct in the Wild when it is known only to survive in cultivation, in captivity or as a naturalized population (or populations) well outside the past range. A taxon is presumed Extinct in the Wild when exhaustive surveys in known and/or expected habitat, at appropriate times (diurnal, seasonal, annual), throughout its historic range have failed to record an individual. Surveys should be over a time frame appropriate to the taxon's life cycle and life form.

CRITICALLY ENDANGERED (CR)

A taxon is Critically Endangered when the best available evidence indicates that it meets any of the criteria A to E for Critically Endangered, and it is therefore considered to be facing an extremely high risk of extinction in the wild.

ENDANGERED (EN)

A taxon is Endangered when the best available evidence indicates that it meets any of the criteria A to E for Endangered, and it is therefore considered to be facing a very high risk of extinction in the wild.

VULNERABLE (VU)

A taxon is Vulnerable when the best available evidence indicates that it meets any of the criteria A to E for Vulnerable, and it is therefore considered to be facing a high risk of extinction in the wild.

NEAR THREATENED (NT)

A taxon is Near Threatened when it has been evaluated against the criteria but does not qualify for Critically Endangered, Endangered or Vulnerable now, but is close to qualifying for or is likely to qualify for a threatened category in the near future.

LEAST CONCERN (LC)

A taxon is Least Concern when it has been evaluated against the criteria and does not qualify for Critically Endangered, Endangered, Vulnerable or Near Threatened. Widespread and abundant taxa are included in this category.

DATA DEFICIENT (DD)

A taxon is Data Deficient when there is inadequate information to make a direct, or indirect, assessment of its risk of extinction based on its distribution and/or population status. A taxon in this category may be well studied, and its biology well known, but appropriate data on abundance and/or distribution are lacking. Data Deficient is therefore not a category of threat. Listing of taxa in this category indicates that more information is required and acknowledges the possibility that future research will show that threatened classification is appropriate. It is important to make positive use of whatever data are available. In many cases great care should be exercised in choosing between DD and a threatened status. If the range of a taxon is suspected to be relatively circumscribed, and a considerable period of time has elapsed since the last record of the taxon, threatened status may well be justified.

NOT EVALUATED (NE)

A taxon is Not Evaluated when it has not yet been evaluated against the criteria.

